

A dispatchable latent heat solar thermophotovoltaic battery

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Abstract

We introduce a conceptual solar-powered latent heat thermophotovoltaic (TPV) battery coupled with beam-down concentrated solar optics for ultra-high temperature ($\sim 1157^\circ\text{C}$) energy storage and conversion. Designed with a modular architecture, the system allows for scalability and flexibility, enabling configurations that meet diverse energy demands. Operating in four distinct modes — charging, discharging, simultaneous charging/discharging, and storage — the system addresses critical challenges associated with modular solar thermal power systems. Minimizing lateral heat and solar-aperture re-emission losses, and selecting TPV cells with bandgaps tailored to the emitter temperature are key elements for an optimized system efficiency. Furthermore, the system's dimensions significantly influence the optical, thermal and conversion performance, affecting radiation distribution, thermal insulation losses, and overall efficiency. Through a multi-physics analysis, the proposed concept seems promising in terms of several metrics, including round-trip efficiency and charging/discharging times, paving, thus, the way as a competitive solution for next-generation solar applications.

Keywords: Latent heat thermophotovoltaic battery; concentrated solar power; silicon alloys, ultra-high temperature energy storage and conversion; optical–thermal–electrical modeling; high temperature thermal emitters

Introduction

Energy storage is an essential component to adopting renewable energy as a source of electricity. Once the challenge of achieving cheap renewable energy is solved (e.g. solar and wind), the next big challenge is to store their energy surpluses and supply them on demand when these resources are not available. Today's installed power storage capacity (~ 272 GW for 2023 as a reference year) accounts only for 3% of current worldwide power generation capacity, being the vast majority ($\sim 67\%$) pumped hydropower¹, which is geographically restricted. Most of the remaining 33% is Li-ion batteries. However, the current high cost of Li-ion batteries makes them only suitable for short-duration storage applications. Therefore, the search for distributed and site-independent low-cost and long duration energy storage solutions is an urgent and important field of research today².

Among the several technological options currently being explored, thermal energy storage (TES) in concentrated solar power (CSP) plants is particularly important. CSP enables the direct storage of solar energy in the form of heat, which can be converted into electricity on demand. By 2023, CSP has deployed 6.7 GW, and another 4 GW were under construction or development in China³. Despite significant progress, CSP technology continues to face a major barrier to further development: its high cost. Although the levelized cost of electricity (LCOE) for CSP has dropped by 70% since 2010, it remains one of the most expensive renewable energy sources at $\$0.117$ per kWh, more than twice the cost of solar photovoltaic (PV) at $\$0.044$ per kWh and onshore wind at $\$0.033$ per kWh⁴. At these costs, it is under debate whether PV plus batteries could be more economical than CSP with thermal storage⁵. This tendency could be exacerbated by the fact that electrochemical batteries are reducing their cost very quickly, thanks to the growing electric vehicle market⁶. Unlike electrochemical batteries, which benefit from diverse niche applications beyond grid-scale energy storage, CSP lacks such alternative markets, making the pursuit of technological breakthroughs particularly critical for its continued development and competitiveness.

Today's CSP technology is mainly built on the same operating principles employed in large, centralized thermal power plants since the early 20th century⁷: the generated heat, produced in this case via concentrated solar energy, is converted into superheated steam to drive a conventional steam turbine that generates electricity. To store solar energy, the generated heat is used to warm a liquid medium, typically a nitrate-based molten salt, which flows from a “cold” tank at $\sim 290^\circ\text{C}$ (minimum) to a “hot” tank at $\sim 565^\circ\text{C}$ (maximum)⁸. The stored sensible heat is later used for electricity production, when sunlight is not available. To reduce the cost, CSP research focuses on increasing the system operating temperature to achieve higher conversion efficiencies⁷. Typical steam Rankine cycles are often limited to a maximum operating temperature of around 600°C . Therefore, advanced Bryton cycle systems and heat transfer fluids (HTF) that are stable at those temperatures (e.g. air or supercritical CO_2)⁹ are

being investigated. Other improvements are directed to use less amounts of building materials to save on materials cost (e.g. search for single-tank storage options)¹⁰. However, to make all these strategies profitable, it is essential to progress through the learning curve of CSP technology, i.e. building commercial installations. Unfortunately, progress in this area is hindered by the very high initial investment costs required for current CSP systems. Most CSP plants necessitate power capacities exceeding a few 10's of megawatts to be profitable. Such large-scale projects demand high capital expenditures (CAPEX), which added to the risk-aversion of financiers on new technologies, result in hindering such investments.

Therefore, efforts are also being made to develop micro-CSP systems^{11,12} that allow for modular and scalable technologies (from residential to utility-scale), enabling investment in smaller plants that do not require large amounts of capital investments. Historically, the CSP systems that have provided the highest efficiency at smaller scales have been dish-engine systems, which have been under development since the mid-1970s¹³. Dish-engine systems, typically sized from 3 to 30 kW, can use high efficiency cycles (e.g., Stirling or Brayton) at high temperatures (600-800°C), and have achieved the highest conversion efficiencies reported so far for CSP (32%)¹⁴. However, when energy storage became an essential value proposition for CSP (due to the rise of solar-PV), the development of dish-engine systems was virtually abandoned. Incorporating storage into dish-engine systems is very challenging^{15,16}, mostly because of the limitations on the weight and size of the storage and engine units, which must be mounted directly on the dish, near the focal point. Thus, most of the current research has shifted towards alternatives based on parabolic trough systems coupled to an organic Rankine cycle (ORC)^{11,12}. These systems operate at very low temperatures (<200°C) and achieve low efficiencies, typically ~7%¹¹. Tower systems, enabling higher temperatures, are a highly efficient alternative for micro-CSP. Nevertheless, very few systems of this kind have been built to date, with examples including the AORA-tulip and the Helios-100 (both 100 kW central-tower plants)¹².

Solid-state energy converters, such as thermoelectrics (TEG), thermionics (TEC), and thermophotovoltaics (TPV), have long been considered as an alternative to dynamic engines for micro-CSP⁹. Unlike dynamic engines, solid-state devices do not require an intermediate conversion of heat into mechanical energy. Thus, they offer the potential for greater reliability and lower maintenance due to the lack of moving parts and working fluids. To date, most of the research has focused on the (most mature) TEG technology, whose low efficiency (typically below 10%) has limited solar-to-heat-to-electricity conversion efficiencies to less than 5%⁹. Much less research effort has been paid to the TPV technology, which holds the highest conversion efficiency among all kinds of solid-state heat converters, in the range of 30–44%¹⁷. Indeed, TPV achieves the highest efficiency at the smallest scale among all kinds of heat converters, including dynamic systems.

TPV devices operate in the same way as solar PV cells^{18,19}: the absorption of photons into a semiconductor material produces electrons that are supplied outwards creating an electric current. The difference lies in the absorption spectrum, which in TPV cells is shifted towards the infrared to efficiently convert thermal radiation instead of solar radiation. To achieve this, low bandgap semiconductor materials are used that can absorb low energy photons, such as germanium (Ge) or indium gallium arsenide (InGaAs). TPV is well suited for CSP because it enables operation at very high temperatures (>1000°C), offers a high efficiency potential (theoretically beyond 50%²⁰), and can deliver several watts per cm² (100's times greater than solar cells). However, very few solar-powered TPV (STPV) systems have been developed so far. The first experimental efficiency for STPV was reported in 2013²¹, and, since then, significant progress has been made until a STPV conversion efficiency record of 8% was achieved in 2015²²⁻²⁴. Although this efficiency may seem small, it has surpassed that of parabolic trough (~7%¹²) and solar-TEG (~5%⁹) systems in less than 5 years of development, and based on very few experimental attempts. As a result, STPV already holds the highest conversion efficiency at the smallest scale among all solar-thermal converters. Combined with its potential to surpass 20%²⁵, STPV is a very appealing alternative for modular/micro-CSP applications.

The integration of thermal energy storage into solar thermophotovoltaic (STPV) systems was first proposed in 1995²⁶, revisited during 2013–2016 considering both latent heat²⁷⁻²⁹ and sensible heat³⁰ options, and experimentally demonstrated for the first time in 2019—albeit using an electric heater rather than concentrated sunlight^{31,32}. Latent heat storage-integrated STPV (LH-SISTPV) systems²⁶⁻²⁹ exploit the extremely high latent heat capacity (>1000 kWh/m³) and melting temperature (>1150°C) of silicon-based phase change materials (PCM), enabling energy storage densities an order of magnitude higher than those of conventional PCMs used in the CSP context, such as sodium nitrate (NaNO₃, 110 kWh/m³) and potassium nitrate (KNO₃, 156 kWh/m³). In addition to their high energy density, silicon-based PCMs offer a remarkably low cost (~\$2/kg), resulting in a stored energy cost of approximately \$4/kWh, about five times lower than that of molten salt-based systems. Finally, their high thermal conductivity values (~20-40 W/mK)^{29,33} enable rapid charge and discharge rates, making them strong PCM candidates for STPV systems — unlike other options examined, such as NaF

whose thermal conductivity is $\sim 1.3 \text{ W/mK}$ ³⁴. The combination of high latent heat and the elevated power density of TPV conversion enables the development of compact and modular systems that integrate both thermal storage and electricity generation within a single unit.

A common characteristic of LH-SISTPV designs is the placement of the storage-conversion unit directly at the focus of a solar concentrator, meaning solar collection, thermal storage, and power conversion are fully coupled. This approach stands in contrast to traditional CSP systems, where these functions are decoupled via heat transfer fluids (HTFs). While full integration offers clear advantages in terms of modularity and system compactness, it introduces new challenges. These include ensuring efficient heat transfer, minimizing radiative losses from the absorber, and—most critically—achieving reliable dispatchability. Because LH-SISTPV systems eliminate the use of HTFs, novel strategies are required to manage the charging and discharging of the thermal storage system in a dispatchable manner—an aspect largely overlooked in early designs. Initial concepts either omitted detailed integration with solar concentrators^{26,28} or proposed overly simplified and impractical solutions, such as the use of fiber optics to deliver concentrated sunlight from a dish to the SISTPV unit^{27,29}.

The purpose of this work is to assess a novel conceptual design for the LH-SISTPV system—one that is modular, scalable, and dispatchable³⁵. Dispatchability is achieved through the relative vertical movement of the system's key components: the PCM and the TPV generator. Key performance indicators (KPIs), including charging efficiency (solar-to-heat), discharging efficiency (heat-to-electricity), and round-trip efficiency (solar-to-electricity), will be evaluated theoretically using computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulations—based on the enthalpy porosity approach already verified in other works³⁶⁻³⁸—combined with detailed balance models for the TPV cells and an optical model for the solar absorber acting as the charging component. Both idealized conditions (e.g., adiabatic insulation and uniform sunlight illumination) and realistic scenarios will be considered to assess the impact of key system non-idealities, including non-uniform sunlight illumination, re-emission losses from the solar cavity to the environment and lateral system losses, on the overall system performance. In addition, critical design parameters—such as the mass of PCM per unit of input solar power (kg/W) and the TPV cell bandgap (eV)—will be explored to identify optimal configurations for maximum system efficiency. For clarity and consistency, the study assumes fixed parameters: a solar concentration factor of 900 suns, a specific PCM (Fe-26.38Si-9.35B, with a melting point of $\sim 1157^\circ\text{C}$ ³³, referred to as FeSiB for simplicity in this study), and a predefined crucible geometry that sets the TPV surface-area-to-PCM-volume ratio at $13.6 \text{ cm}^2/\text{cm}^3$ independent of crucible height.

The paper is structured as follows. We start describing the system architecture, including the core assumptions and design rationale. We continue presenting the transient charging and discharging behavior of a reference system using 0.74 eV TPV cells and $\sim 0.19 \text{ W/g}$ of PCM mass per unit of input solar power, with a focus on time-resolved power output and efficiency metrics. Then, we expand the analysis to a broader parameter space, evaluating the impact of TPV cell bandgap and PCM loading (g/W) on system performance, with the goal of identifying optimal design points. Finally, we conclude the article with the main results.

The Appendix section includes detailed information on the used numerical models and input parameters. The Supplementary results section includes results for a list of the 73 studied cases (C.5. Summary of simulated cases) and detailed results of the involved system losses and involved KPIs.

Results and discussion

System Design, Geometry and Performance Indicators

This section presents the key aspects of the system design and the primary variables used to evaluate its performance. While the description provided is not exhaustive, it aims to offer a clear and concise overview. For a more detailed account of the system's design, operational modes, and material selection, readers are referred to Detailed concept description: System simulation.

The LH-SISTPV system design³² that is assessed in this work is powered by a heliostat field that collects and concentrates solar radiation onto a mirror suspended high above the central receiver, as illustrated in Figure 1A. This elevated mirror redirects the concentrated sunlight downward (“beam-down”) toward the ground, where it irradiates the SISTPV system at a significant concentration ratio ($C \approx 900$ suns). Beam-down solar concentrators are capable of achieving high concentration ratios at both large and small scales^{14,39}, and critically, they allow for the use of stationary receivers. This feature is especially advantageous for the LH-SISTPV system, which incorporates PCMs.

To further enhance the local solar flux, the LH-SISTPV system can incorporate multiple secondary concentrators, such as compound parabolic concentrators (CPC), which channel the incoming radiation into a series of solar absorbers formed by cylindrical cavities (labeled “2”

in Figure 1). A transparent window is positioned atop the absorber apertures, allowing for a sealed environment that maintains a clean internal atmosphere.

(A)

(B)

Figure 1. LH-SISTPV concept including the solar field and its key sub-components (A) and details of the receiver/storage unit (top, isometric, bottom and side views) (B) 1 (orange regions): PCM, 2: cylindrical cavity, 3: rectangular cavity.

Within the system, several graphite containers or “crucibles” store a metal-based PCM (labeled “1” in Figure 1B) for latent heat energy storage (LHTES). Each crucible features four flat walls and four inwardly curved, semi-cylindrical walls. When assembled together, the semi-cylindrical walls collectively form cylindrical cavities that function as the solar absorbers, while the flat walls align to create rectangular parallelepiped cavities intended to house the TPV generators, which also has a rectangular parallelepiped shape (labeled “3” in Figure 1). The rectangular graphite walls serve as the TPV emitting surfaces.

The TPV generator consists of a parallelepiped-shaped holder, with each of its four faces populated by TPV cells. These cells generate electricity by converting incandescent radiation from the TPV emitter into electrical energy via the photovoltaic effect. However, only photons with energies exceeding the semiconductor bandgap of the TPV cells contribute to electricity generation. To enhance efficiency, each cell is equipped with a back-surface reflector (BSR) that redirects sub-bandgap (low-energy) photons back toward the crucible, where they can be reabsorbed. Additionally, the TPV holder integrates a water-cooled thermal dissipator to prevent cell overheating, thereby reducing associated efficiency losses.

A key feature of the system is the vertical mobility of both the crucibles and TPV generators, allowing them to be repositioned or retracted as needed. The TPV generator can occupy three discrete vertical positions—top, middle, and bottom—while the crucible is limited to two positions: top and middle. Alignment between the crucible and the TPV generator occurs only when both are at the same vertical level (either top or middle), and these aligned positions correspond to system discharge modes, where the TPV generator converts stored thermal energy from the crucible into electricity.

Figure 2. Operating modes of the LH-SISTPV concept (A) Mode C/D, (B) Mode C, (C) Mode D, and, (D) Mode S. (isometric view).

When the crucible is in the uppermost position, it is exposed to the solar aperture, enabling it to absorb concentrated solar energy for charging. However, this exposure also introduces potential thermal losses due to radiative heat escape through the aperture. In contrast, when the crucible is at the middle position, it is thermally insulated from the aperture, and can only exchange heat with the TPV generator—provided the TPV is also at the middle position. This vertical mobility forms the basis for four distinct operational modes, illustrated in Figure 2, two modes for day-time operation (C/D, C) and two for night-time operation (D, S):

- **Mode C/D** (Figure 2A): Simultaneous Charge/Discharge (Daytime). Both, the crucible and the TPV generator, are positioned at their uppermost vertical location. Solar radiation is heating through the absorber the cylindrical sidewalls of the crucibles (charging), whereas the TPV is patched to the crucible flat walls, producing power simultaneously (discharging). This mode involves re-emission losses from the solar aperture to the ambient and lateral emission losses from the crucible upper and bottom surfaces.
- **Mode C** (Figure 2B): Charge-only (Daytime). The crucible is positioned at its uppermost point, while the TPV generator is located at its mid-level position. The system is charged likewise Mode A, but the TPV is dispatched (OFF). As in Mode A, thermal losses originate from the solar aperture (re-emission losses) and the crucible upper and bottom surfaces (lateral losses). Additional losses originate from the crucible inner sidewalls - forming the TPV cavity- towards the upper surface of the TPV holder, eventually dissipating to the environment. This loss is influenced by the average view factor of the holder's upper surface area to the inner crucible sidewall area, which can be approximated as the ratio of their surface areas.
- **Mode D** (Figure 2C): Discharge-only (Night-time). The crucible is positioned at its lowest point, while the TPV generator is at its mid-level position, aligned with the crucible. The heat in the crucibles is being discharged through the TPV, whereas the crucibles are retracted from the stationary solar concentrator to avoid re-emission losses. An insulation material in the form of cylinder is introduced in the hollow solar absorber cavity, when the crucible is in its middle position, in order to eliminate re-emission losses. Thus, the main losses in this mode originate from the crucible upper and bottom surfaces (lateral losses).
- **Mode S** (Figure 2D): Storage-only (Night-time). Both the crucible and the TPV generator are positioned at their lowest vertical location. The TPV is OFF (dispatched from the crucibles) and the system simply stores thermal energy. In this mode, the thermal insulation plays a key role on how much time the system will sustain its energy. Thermal losses in this mode originate from the crucible upper and bottom surfaces, as well as the inner crucible walls forming the TPV cavity, likewise mode B.

Due to the cavity's design open on the top, radiative re-emission losses ($Q_{abs,losses}$) occur, allowing thermal radiation to escape to the environment. While these excess losses are inherent to open cavity configurations, they become more pronounced under non-uniform heat flux conditions, as certain regions within the absorber cavity may overheat, leading to increased re-emission losses. This effect is especially significant when higher heat flux densities are present near the upper part of the solar absorber, as in our studied system. This in turn might adversely

affect the system charging efficiency. Finally, the system might experience thermal losses through its sidewalls during all possible operating modes, even when effective insulation is used. To minimize heat losses, the system includes thermal insulation materials (TIMs), such as Alumina Fiber Mat (AFM)⁴⁰ and Fumed Silica Board (FSB)⁴⁰, to prevent heat escaping from the system during the different modes of operation. TIMs are found (see Figure 20 and Figure 21) at the top (AFM) and bottom (AFM and FSB) surfaces of the crucibles, to eliminate lateral thermal losses during all operating modes, and at the upper part of the TPV holder (a combination of AFM with an additional reflecting thin material), to avoid heat losses through the TPV cavity when the TPV generator is retracted at its mid and bottom positions. For more information, see at *System sub-components*, Table 9.

The performance of the system will be monitored through a series of KPIs, listed in Table 1. Two types of efficiencies are considered in this work. The first one is the instantaneous efficiency (or power-based efficiency), η , defined as the ratio of the output to the input power (in Watts and noted as \dot{Q} at a specific moment in time). The second one is the integrated efficiency (or energy-based efficiency), $\bar{\eta}$, which is defined as the ratio of the total output energy (in Wh) to the total input energy (in Wh) over a given time interval.

Table 1. Summary of the KPIs used in this study.

KPI	Mode(s)	Description	Definition [units]
β	All	Liquid fraction – the ratio of the PCM liquid mass, m_{L-PCM} , to the total PCM mass, m_{PCM} .	$\frac{m_{L-PCM} \text{ [kg]}}{m_{PCM} \text{ [kg]}}$
$\frac{d\beta}{dt}$	All	Liquid fraction time gradient – Equivalent to the charging/discharging rate	$\frac{\beta(t_2) - \beta(t_1) \text{ [-]}}{t_2 - t_1 \text{ [s]}}$
$\eta_{prod}^{(2)}$	C/D	Production efficiency - The ratio of the produced electric power, P_{el} , to the incoming solar radiation, \dot{Q}_{in}	$\frac{P_{el}}{\dot{Q}_{in}} \text{ [-]}$
$\eta_{abs}^{(2)}$	C/D, C	Absorber efficiency - the ratio of the net heat flux at the solar absorber, $\dot{Q}_{in,abs,net} = \dot{Q}_{in} - \dot{Q}_{abs,losses}$, to the incoming radiation \dot{Q}_{in}	$\frac{\dot{Q}_{in} - \dot{Q}_{abs,losses}}{\dot{Q}_{in}} \text{ [-]}$
$\eta_c^{(2)}$	C/D, C	Charging efficiency - The ratio of the net stored thermal energy $\dot{Q}_{in,net}$, to the incoming solar radiation, \dot{Q}_{in} .	$\frac{\dot{Q}_{in,net}}{\dot{Q}_{in}} \text{ [-]}$
$\eta_{TPV}^{(2)}$	C/D, D	TPV efficiency - the ratio of the produced electric power, P_{el} , to the radiated heat absorbed in the TPV generator, \dot{Q}_{TPV}	$\frac{P_{el}}{\dot{Q}_{TPV}} \text{ [-]}$
$\eta_{d,th}^{(2)}$	C/D, D	Discharging thermal efficiency - The ratio of the radiated heat absorbed in the TPV to the released power, $\dot{Q}_{out}^{(1)}$	$\frac{\dot{Q}_{TPV}}{\dot{Q}_{out}} \text{ [-]}$
$\eta_{d,el}^{(2)}$	C/D, D	Discharge electric efficiency - the ratio of the produced electric power, P_{el} , to the released power \dot{Q}_{out}	$\frac{P_{el}}{\dot{Q}_{out}} \text{ [-]}$
$\bar{\eta}_{RT}$	C&D	System round trip efficiency – The ratio of the total electric power produced, \bar{P}_{el} , to the total incoming solar radiation, \dot{Q}_{in} , over a complete charging-discharging cycle ⁽³⁾	$\frac{\bar{P}_{el}}{\dot{Q}_{in}} = \bar{\eta}_c \bar{\eta}_{d,el} \text{ [-]}$
<i>SOC</i>	C/D, C, D	System state of charge – The fraction of latent heat stored in the system, approximated as equal as β	$\beta \text{ [-]}$
<i>Ste</i>	C/D, C	Stefan number – The ratio of sensible, $Q_{sensible,PCM}$, to latent heat, $Q_{latent,PCM}$, stored in the storage system	$[-]$
t_{pr}	C/D, C	PCM pre-heating time from an initial temperature T_0 until the PCM melting point	$[\text{s}]$
t_c	C/D, C	Time needed after the preheating phase for the PCM to melt completely ($\beta=1$)	$[\text{s}]$
t_{eq}	C/D	Time needed for the LHTPV battery to reach quasi steady-state conditions with its total \dot{Q}_{in} balancing its total \dot{Q}_{out}	$[\text{s}]$
t_d	D, S	The time required for the PCM to fully solidify, i.e., until the solid fraction reaches $\beta = 0$.	$[\text{s}]$
t_{stor}	S	Time needed for the system to lose all its stored latent heat energy and, thus, the PCM to solidify completely ($\beta=0$) starting from a liquid state ($\beta=1$)	$[\text{s}]$
t_{RT}	C&D	System cycling time – Time needed for the system do undertake a full cycling period charging/discharging ⁽³⁾	$t_c + t_d \text{ [s]}$

⁽¹⁾ the outgoing heat Q_{out} is the sum of the "valuable" outgoing heat to the TPV, Q_{TPV} , the system losses, Q_{losses} (which accounts for the lateral losses from the PCM and the rest of the system component (e.g. water-cooled CPC) and, the absorber re-emission losses, $Q_{abs,losses}$. ⁽²⁾ Units in W/W (for the instantaneous efficiency) or in Wh/Wh (for the integrated efficiency) ⁽³⁾ the PCM pre-heating is not considered

Time-resolved power output and efficiency

In this section we present detailed time-resolved results for the four possible operating modes of a benchmark system featuring low band-gap ($E_g=0.74$ eV) InGaAs cells and a crucible height of $H_c=0.48$ m. During charging modes (C/D and C), this system receives ~ 1 MW/m³_{PCM} (or ~ 0.19 W/g) through the solar absorber sidewalls with a non-uniform heat flux profile. Across all operating modes, the system is subject to lateral heat losses, while in charging modes, the solar absorber also experiences unavoidable re-emission losses to the ambient.

To quantify the effect of the input heat flux distribution on the system performance, two scenarios are analyzed: an ideal case (“Uniform”) and a realistic one (“Non-Uniform”). In the “Non-Uniform” scenario, representative of real operating conditions, the solar absorber sidewalls are subjected to a constant input power, \dot{Q}_{in} , with a non-uniform distribution (with higher heat flux values being present at the upper part of the solar absorber cavity and lower towards its bottom part). As the system temperature rises, the net input solar power, $\dot{Q}_{in,abs,net}$, decreases due to re-emission losses from the solar cavity to the environment, $\dot{Q}_{abs,losses}$. In the “Uniform” case, the same input power value, \dot{Q}_{in} , is uniformly distributed across the absorber surface, leading in principle to a more uniform temperature profile. This, in turn, can lead to lower re-emission losses, $\dot{Q}_{abs,losses}$ and, thus, higher charging efficiencies, η_c . Added to this, two physically unrealistic situations are introduced in our analysis: the “zero re-emission” and “adiabatic” conditions cases. The “zero re-emission” assumption considers zero re-emission losses ($\dot{Q}_{abs,losses} = 0$) from the solar cavity to the environment, in contrast to the “re-emission” scenario, in which re-emission losses are accounted for. The case “adiabatic” assumes zero lateral heat losses ($\dot{Q}_{losses} = 0$) from the system components to the ambient and the “non-adiabatic” considers system losses in the analysis.

In Mode C/D -which operates as both a charging and discharging mode- we examine the influence of the TPV cell band-gap across four test cases (0.55, 0.74, 0.90, and 1.1 eV). Additionally, we assess the impact of the solar absorber heat flux profile by comparing the “Uniform” and “Non-Uniform” cases. In all discharging cases studied (both in Modes C/D and D), the TPV cells are assumed to incorporate a back-surface reflector with reflectivity 0.98, in order to increase the TPV efficiency, η_{TPV} .

In charging Mode C, we thoroughly examine the impact of three key factors on the system’s thermal performance: (1) the solar absorber heat flux (illumination) profile by comparing the “Uniform” and “Non-Uniform” cases, (2) the re-emission losses from the solar absorber to the environment, and (3) the lateral heat losses from the system components to the ambient.

In discharging Mode D, we focus on the TPV converter, which is the main component determining the system discharging efficiency. The discharging efficiency in a TPV system is highly sensitive to the band-gap energy of the photovoltaic material. In this regard, we evaluate the reference case of 0.74 eV against alternative band-gap values, covering a range from low-band gap (0.55 eV) to higher band-gap (0.9 eV and 1.1 eV) cells. We also compare these cases with adiabatic scenarios ($\dot{Q}_{losses} = 0$), in order to address the effect of the lateral system losses during the discharging mode, as well.

In Mode S, we examine the system losses during the storage (or self-discharging) phase, until the LHTES fully depletes its contained latent heat content.

Finally, we also analyze the full operating cycle (Modes C and D), focusing on the impact of two key factors on the system round-trip efficiency and total charging-discharging time: (1) the solar absorber heat flux (illumination) profile, and (2) the re-emission losses from the solar absorber to the environment. For this analysis, the TPV cell band-gap is set to 0.74 eV.

Mode C/D

During Mode C/D, the system simultaneously charges from the solar absorber with an input power \dot{Q}_{in} and discharges through the TPV cell with a net TPV flux \dot{Q}_{TPV} . Therefore, this mode reaches a steady-state condition when the total outgoing power \dot{Q}_{out} -including \dot{Q}_{TPV} , lateral heat losses \dot{Q}_{losses} and absorber re-emission losses $\dot{Q}_{abs,losses}$ - balances the input power \dot{Q}_{in} . In this state, the melting fraction of the PCM depends highly on the relative value of \dot{Q}_{in} ($=\dot{Q}_{out}$) to \dot{Q}_{TPV} . In order to balance both the “valuable” \dot{Q}_{TPV} and the system losses ($\dot{Q}_{losses} + \dot{Q}_{abs,losses}$) the $\dot{Q}_{in}/\dot{Q}_{TPV}$ ratio should be at least 1.5. If the \dot{Q}_{in} relatively to \dot{Q}_{TPV} is low ($\dot{Q}_{TPV}/\dot{Q}_{in} > 0.6$, Figure 3C), the steady-state melting fraction could be lower than 1, i.e. the PCM is partially melted. Depending on the TPV cell bandgap (E_g), the steady-state \dot{Q}_{TPV} values range from ~ 13.2 kW ($E_g = 0.55$ eV) to 8.8 kW ($E_g = 1.1$ eV). Intermediate bandgaps (0.74 eV and 0.90 eV) receive ~ 11.4 kW and ~ 9.4 kW, respectively. With low-band gap cells (0.55 eV), \dot{Q}_{TPV} is high, resulting in a high $\dot{Q}_{TPV}/\dot{Q}_{in}$ ratio (> 0.6). As a consequence, the system losses must be low in order to fulfill the energy balance, especially the solar absorber re-emission losses. However, for the current insulation material properties and solar flux heat flux profile, the only way for the \dot{Q}_{in} to balance the heat losses and the \dot{Q}_{TPV} is to operate the system at lower temperatures, resulting in a reduced volume-averaged PCM temperature. Therefore, the system reaches equilibrium conditions with a partially melted PCM ($\beta < 1$), Figure 3A. On the

other hand, for 0.74 eV cells, full melting occurs after ~ 12 hours, reaching steady state at ~ 14 hours. At higher bandgaps (0.90–1.10 eV), melting occurs faster (< 8 h) due to lower \dot{Q}_{TPV} , but reaching steady-state takes longer post-melting, Figure 3B, C.

Results also indicate that the band-gap cell values highly affect the system performance, Figure 3B. Among the cases studied, the lowest band-gap (0.55 eV) achieves the highest instantaneous production efficiency, η_{prod} , approaching 28% under uniform and 26% under non-uniform conditions, whilst the highest band-gap (1.10 eV) yields the lowest performance due to a reduced photon absorption – 5.4% and 7.72% efficiency for the uniform and non-uniform flux conditions, near the PCM melting point ($T=1157^\circ\text{C}$, $\beta = 1$). In the reference case (0.74 eV), the production efficiency during the PCM melting process ranges within ~ 6.4 -24% (“non-uniform” profile), and ~ 13 -23% (“uniform” profile).

Notably, the solar absorber’s heat flux profile affects the system production efficiency and charging time. Results indicate that a “uniform” heating significantly enhances system performance, leading to higher peak efficiencies and faster response time, especially for low band gap cells (0.55-0.74 eV). For this profile, the melting front is developing from the crucible outer surfaces to the core in a rather uniform profile resulting in a more balanced phase-change process, Figure 3D. With this “uniform” profile, the lower re-emission losses at the upper absorber section enhance production efficiency and accelerate melting compared to a “non-uniform” profile.

Figure 3. Mode C/D: (A) β , (B) η_{prod} , and (C) $\dot{Q}_{TPV}/\dot{Q}_{in}$ ratio with time (24 h period), and (D) contours of β (non-uniform vs. uniform absorber profile for $E_g=0.74\text{ eV}$). In the graphs: solid/dotted: Non-Uniform/Uniform absorber profile.

On the contrary, the “non-uniform” profile leads to a vertically developed phase-change front, forming a stratified liquid-solid structure—with liquid PCM accumulating at the top and solid PCM remaining at the bottom. While this stratification may create a larger temperature gradient and thereby improve heat transfer, especially at the beginning of the phase-changing process, the presence of excess re-emission losses negatively affects the charging time and η_{prod} . Notably, for low band gap cells, i.e. 0.55 eV, in which the $\dot{Q}_{TPV}/\dot{Q}_{in}$ is higher than 60% and the PCM remains partially solid within the system operation, the “uniform” profile results in a higher PCM liquid fraction ($\beta \sim 0.72$) with contrast to the “non-uniform” profile ($\beta \sim 0.32$) near steady-state conditions. This is expected since reduced re-emission losses lead to a higher stored energy in the PCM and a higher volume-averaged PCM temperature. Nevertheless, the steady-state conditions for the “uniform” profile take a period of more than 24 hours to be reached. A more thorough analysis concerning the heat losses can be found in the Appendix Section (*Heat losses analysis*).

Mode C

During Mode C the system charges from the solar absorber with an input flux \dot{Q}_{in} and experiences re-emission losses to the environment from the solar absorber cavity, $\dot{Q}_{abs,losses}$ and lateral thermal losses from its sidewalls \dot{Q}_{losses} , likewise Mode C/D. Results in this case indicate that the heat flux profile of the solar absorber can have a high influence on the system charging rate $d\beta/dt$ over time (Figure 4A), as in Mode C/D, especially when re-emission losses from the solar aperture come into play.

In the “non-uniform” profile that uses realistic absorbers (including re-emission losses), we can notice a relative lower charging rate if it is to be compared with the “uniform” profile, mostly because of the high re-emission losses originating from the higher part of the solar absorber. This can be also reflected by the net thermal energy, \dot{Q}_{net} entering into the system, Figure 4B. It has been revealed that the re-emission losses originating from the solar aperture $\dot{Q}_{abs,losses}$, determine more the system charging efficiency, η_c , than the system lateral losses, \dot{Q}_{losses} . This can be deduced by comparing the \dot{Q}_{net} in the “zero re-emission” cases (blue and green lines) with the “re-emission” cases (red and purple lines). Near the ending point of the PCM melting the $\dot{Q}_{net,min} / \dot{Q}_{in}$ ratio is over 0.9 for the “zero re-emission” cases, and, close to 0.6 (uniform profile) and 0.45 (non-uniform profile) for the “re-emission” cases. Notably, the effect of “non-uniform” to “uniform” cases can be observed only in the real case scenario, in which the solar absorber losses are accounted for.

Figure 4. Mode C: (A) Charging rate vs. time. (B) Net incoming heat ratio per PCM mass with time (circular elements indicate the onset and finishing point of the phase changing phenomenon per case) (C) Flow contours ($\beta=0.2, 0.5$ and 0.8)

An interesting result is that the system charging rate reaches for all cases a peak value and then starts declining. This is attributed to the fact that at the beginning of the PCM melting, a liquid film is formed -at the crucible upper part in the non-uniform profile and at the crucible sidewalls in the uniform profile, Figure 4C -and the PCM charging rate starts to increase. After some point in which the PCM liquid mass becomes comparable to the PCM solid mass, part of the heat is converted into sensible heat “slowing down” the PCM melting rate. In the non-uniform profile this phenomenon is more evident, owing to the highest amounts of heat provided at the upper part of the PCM. On the one hand, this is favourable since the PCM melting phenomenon starts quicker than in the uniform profile, on the other hand the PCM charging rate declines really fast, for rather low PCM melting fractions. This is also noticed even for the “zero re-emission” case. This indicates that a uniform solidification–melting profile-characterized by a phase-change front advancing uniformly from the crucible sidewalls to the core- leads to a greater system charging rate compared to a vertically stratified solid–liquid structure. This observation applies likewise for Mode C/D.

Mode D

During mode D, the system discharges through the TPV cell with a net flux \dot{Q}_{TPV} . For the benchmark case, where “non-adiabatic” conditions occur, the system discharges within 2.5 to 14 hours approximately depending on the chosen TPV cell band gap (E_g), Figure 5A. For low-band gaps (0.55 eV), we can achieve fast discharging conditions of almost 2.57 hours. For high band-gap cells (1.10 eV) the discharging time is around 14 hours. Notably, for band gaps higher than 0.74 eV the heat losses start to play a significant role, owing to the low discharging times. This is for instance why the discharging time deviation, $t_{d,dev}$, between the non-adiabatic and adiabatic conditions for higher-band gap cells can surpass 10% (for instance for $E_g=1.1$ eV $t_{d,dev}$ is around 26%), whereas for TPV cells with $E_g < 0.74$ eV this deviation is less than 6.6%.

Regarding the solidification phenomenon in the specific arrangement tested, the solid-liquid front initiates from the sidewalls of the PCM crucible and gradually advances to the core of the PCM, Figure 5 B. This process is primarily conduction-driven, although buoyancy-driven natural convection might negatively impact the growth of the solid phase, particularly in the early stages of solidification⁴¹. However, this effect is relatively minor compared to heat transfer through conduction^{42,43}, especially when the system is studied on a macroscopic scale as in the present study. Thus, in this case, the only factors that influence the system discharging behaviour are the TPV cell conversion efficiency η_{TPV} , the PCM and crucible thermal properties and the insulating material thickness.

As it could be expected, the highest net heat flux extraction is observed for the TPV cells with the lowest band-gap (0.55 eV), Figure 5C. Specifically, the maximum and minimum \dot{Q}_{TPV} values for the 0.55 eV case are nearly twice as high as those for the 0.74 eV case and three

times higher than those for the 0.90 eV case. The lowest heat flux extraction occurs with high band gap cells (1.1 eV), which exhibit values nearly six times lower than the 0.55 eV case. Under the tested operating conditions, the highest maximum instantaneous TPV efficiencies are observed for TPV cells with $E_g=0.74$ eV, followed by those with $E_g=0.90$ eV, Figure 5D. TPV cells with an intermediate bandgap value of 0.74 eV tend to have the highest instantaneous “non-adiabatic” and “adiabatic” scenarios.

Figure 5. Mode D (A) β vs. time and (B) β contours ($\beta=0.2, 0.5$ and 0.8) at different time instants for $E_g=0.74$ eV, and, (C) \dot{Q}_{TPV} (W/cm²), (D) P_{el} (W/cm²) and (E) $\eta_{d,el}$ vs. time (solid line: non-adiabatic case, dotted line: adiabatic case, $\eta_{TPV,min}/\eta_{TPV,max}$: minimum and maximum TPV efficiency).

A key metric demonstrating the system discharging performance is the discharge electric efficiency, $\eta_{d,el}$, Figure 5E. It should be noted that the discharge electric efficiency in the adiabatic scenario coincides with the TPV efficiency η_{TPV} , as $\dot{Q}_{out}=\dot{Q}_{TPV}$. It can be seen that for “non-adiabatic” conditions InGaAs cells of $E_g=0.74$ eV have higher $\eta_{d,el}$ than these of $E_g=0.55$ eV during the phenomenon evolution and the highest from all the band-gaps tested. For the “non-adiabatic” scenario the system losses balance the discharge electric efficiencies for the lower band-gap cells (0.55 and 0.74 eV) after 1 hour approximately of the PCM melting. The integral discharge conversion efficiency $\bar{\eta}_{d,el}$ for the “non-adiabatic” case scenario varies from $\sim 36.7\%$ ($E_g=0.55$ eV) and $\sim 36.1\%$ ($E_g=0.74$ eV) down to $\sim 29.7\%$ ($E_g=0.90$ eV) and $\sim 16.8\%$ ($E_g=1.10$ eV). Accordingly, the integral conversion efficiency $\bar{\eta}_{TPV}$, for the TPV cells with $E_g=0.74$ eV is equal to $\sim 41.2\%$, followed by the TPV cells of $E_g=0.55$ eV ($\sim 39.4\%$) and then TPV cells of $E_g=0.90$ eV ($\sim 37.1\%$). The worst case is the TPV cells of $E_g=1.1$ eV ($\sim 24.4\%$). These values, are close to the η_{TPV} efficiencies at the melting point of the PCM ($\sim 1150^\circ\text{C}$). This finding leads to the conclusion that for the specific or similar arrangements (for instance of crucible height of 0.48 m) of TPV emitter temperatures operating close to 1100-1200°C InGaAs TPV cells of band-gap close to 0.74 represent an optimal and practical solution in terms of the TPV conversion efficiency.

Mode S

Mode S is a storage mode, which can be also considered as a self-discharging mode, as the system gradually loses its stored energy - primarily in the form of latent heat, $Q_{latent,PCM}$, and to a lesser extent as sensible heat. In the reference case, the ratio of $Q_{latent,PCM}$ to the total system thermal losses, Q_{losses} , for a full discharging time, i.e. from the onset of the self-discharging mode right until after the full PCM solidification, is approximately 86%. Additionally, the storage time, t_{stor} , is around 18.8 hours demonstrating the system’s ability to retain usable thermal energy through an extended period—potentially covering an entire night or few hours without solar input.

Scaling-up the system ($H_c > 0.5$ m) is expected to slow-down the self-discharging process. In the current system scale, the majority of the heat losses originate from the TPV cavity by 58.3% (i.e. the heat that escapes from the TPV emitter walls through the TPV cell holder). When the system is scaled up, the surface area of the TPV emitter's lateral walls increases proportionally. As a result, the view factor of the TPV emitter walls to the TPV holder upper part will decrease (since the TPV holder's upper surface remains constant regardless of the crucible height), leading to a reduction in heat losses over a specific time interval.

Table 2. Summary of results for the envisaged system (Mode S, $H_c=0.48$ m).

Section i	TPV cavity	Insulation Bottom	Insulation Up	t_{stor} (h)	Q_{losses} (MJ)	Q_{losses}/m_{PCM} (MJ/kg)	$Q_{latent,PCM}/Q_{losses}$ (-)
Q_i/Q_{losses} (%)	58.43	11.24	30.31	18.84	-94	-0.90	0.86

The remaining losses are lateral thermal losses through the insulating materials at the system's upper section—covering the top of the PCM container and the solar absorber cavity (Insulation Up)—and the bottom of the PCM container (Insulation Bottom), Table 2. These losses are primarily dependent on the insulating materials properties used in the current system, but they are also influenced by the overall scale of the system (More information about the insulating material properties selection can be found in *System sub-components*).

Full Cycle Period: Modes C & D

A full cycling period entails full charging of the system (mode C) until it melts completely ($\beta=1$), and, then, immediate switching on the discharging mode D (energy harvesting from the TPV converter). During system charging (Mode C), we notice two stages as in Mode C/D, which are the system preheating until the PCMs melting point and, then onset of the phase-changing phenomenon until complete melting of the PCM. In our reference case ($H_c=0.48$ m), which includes a non-uniform absorber heat flux profile with re-emission losses to the environment and lateral system losses, we can identify 3 factors that might hinder the system storage performance: i. absorber heat flux profile, ii. re-emission losses and iii. lateral system losses. Especially the reemission losses are unavoidable independent on the other two factors. In order to identify the effect of these three factors we compare four cases, i.e. the “non-uniform”, “re-emission” (reference) case, ii. the “uniform”, “re-emission” case, the iii. “non-uniform”, “zero re-emission” case and the iv. “uniform”, “zero re-emission” case. In all cases, the “non-adiabatic” scenario is applied, whereas a TPV converter with InGaAs cells of $E_g=0.74$ eV is used for the system discharging.

Depending on the solar absorber heat flux profile, the system cycling time, t_{rt} , can vary up to 10% from 10.14 h for the reference case to 9.17 h for the uniform profile, Figure 6A. Concerning the solar absorber re-emission losses, results indicate that in the case of the non-uniform profile there is a higher difference from the (unrealistic) case without re-emission losses in terms of system total cycling time (12.52%), than in the case of the uniform case (7%). This can be attributed to the fact that in the reference case the heat flux density is higher at the absorbed upper part, leading to higher re-emission losses to the environment. This is the reason why the overall absorber efficiency for the uniform profile (~74%) is almost 12% higher than the non-uniform profile (~65%), Figure 6B.

Figure 6. Modes C & D: (A) SOC vs. time for modes C and D (solid line: charging state, dashed line: discharging state) and (B) System efficiency vs. time (solid line: η_c (charging efficiency), dashed line: $\eta_{d,el}$ (discharge electric conversion efficiency)).

Even still, for all tested cases the system round-trip efficiency, $\bar{\eta}_{RT}$ is more than 20 %. The calculated $\bar{\eta}_{RT}$ value for the reference case (21%) indicates a strong potential for the system to surpass today's solar to heat to power conversion systems. Additionally, it has been shown that there is room for further improvement—particularly by optimizing the solar absorber's heat flux profile and reducing re-emission losses from the solar absorber to the environment. Minimizing lateral heat losses, Q_{losses} , could also help increase the round-trip efficiency.

However, their impact appears to be less significant compared to the solar absorber's re-emission losses. In fact, in cases where the solar absorber re-emission losses are not accounted for (Cases 3 and 4), the system's charging efficiency, η_c , reaches approximately 93% for both absorber profiles. This suggests that total thermal losses are less than 7% relative to the system's input energy.

Table 3. Summary of results for a full cycle (Modes C&D)– $E_g=0.74$ eV, $H_c=0.48$ m.

Case	Heat flux profile	Losses absorber	t_{pr} (h)	t_c (h)	t_d (h)	$\bar{\eta}_{abs}$ (%)	$\bar{\eta}_c$ (%)	$\bar{\eta}_{TPV}$ (%)	$\bar{\eta}_{d,el}$ (%)	$\bar{\eta}_{RT}$ (%)
1 (Ref)	Non-Uniform	ν	2.01	3.62		64.9	58.1			20.99
2	Uniform	ν	2.44	2.22	4.51	73.6	67.1	41.2	36.12	24.23
3	Non-Uniform	x	1.58	2.78		100	92.9			33.55
4	Uniform	x	2.26	1.75		100	93.2			33.66

Impact of TPV Bandgap and Crucible Height on System Performance

After detailing the critical time varying variables of the studied system, we present the results of a multi-parametric study examining the influence of the crucible height, H_c -linked to the PCM loading, in g per W of solar input- and TPV cell band gap, E_g , on the overall system performance. Key global parameters used to evaluate the overall system performance include for Mode C/D (a) charging time, t_c , (b) time to reach quasi-steady state conditions, t_{eq} , (c) integrated production efficiency, $\bar{\eta}_{prod}$, and (d) latent heat storage ratio, $Q_{latent,PCM}/Q_{in}$. For Modes C, D and S the system is assessed through its: (a) charging-discharging-storage time, (b) latent heat storage ratio, (c) TPV efficiency, and (d) solar absorber efficiency. Each operating mode is presented individually, followed by results for a complete charging-discharging cycle in which the (a) full charging-discharging time, t_{RT} , and (b) round-trip efficiency, $\bar{\eta}_{RT}$, are used as parameters of comparison. Notably, since the objective is to assess the overall system behavior when varying the crucible height and TPV cell band gap, all efficiency values are reported as time-integrated quantities to capture the cumulative performance over the full operating period across each Mode.

Mode C/D

The performance of Mode A is highly influenced by the combination of 3 key parameters, i.e. the crucible height, the solar absorber illumination profile and the TPV cell band-gap, Figures 7A-C present results of the uniform absorber profile for different system design parameters and Figures 7D-F for the non-uniform absorber profile. Detailed results can be also found in (*Heat losses analysis: Mode C/D*). Results indicate that this mode can achieve the highest production efficiency for tall crucibles ($H_c \geq 0.48$ m) and low band-gap energies for the TPV cell (< 0.74 eV), approaching in some cases values close to 25%. However, despite the high efficiency, this low-bandgap and tall-crucible combination may result in low latent heat storage or excessively long charging times. This is attributed to the combination of large PCM volumes and high TPV heat extraction, which difficult the melting of the entire volume of the PCM.

Profile	$H_c = 0.72$ m, $E_g = 0.55$ eV	$H_c = 0.72$ m, $E_g = 0.74$ eV	$H_c = 0.48$ m, $E_g = 0.55$ eV	Rest of the cases
Uniform	$\beta_{max}=0$	$\beta_{max}=0.82$	$\beta_{max}=0.72$	$\beta_{max}=1$
NonUniform	$\beta_{max}=0.03$	$\beta_{max}=0.52$	$\beta_{max}=0.3$	$\beta_{max}=1$

Figure 7. Mode C/D: Contour graphs of (A) and (D): β_{max} , (B) and (E): $\bar{\eta}_{prod}$, and (C) and (F): overall $Q_{latent,PCM}/Q_{stored}$ ratio for different H_c and TPV E_g values. (β_{max} : maximum liquid fraction in the system by

observing the full storage behaviour until quasi steady-state conditions are reached. Graphs A-C: uniform solar absorber profile, Graphs D-F: non-uniform absorber profile).

For instance, for relatively tall crucible heights (~ 0.72 m) and low-band gap cells ($E_g=0.55$ eV), the production efficiency remains high ($\sim 17\%$ for the uniform, Figure 7B, and $\sim 26\%$ for the non-uniform absorber profile, Figure 7E). However, the system reaches quasi-equilibrium conditions at ~ 10.6 h (non-uniform profile) and ~ 7.4 h (uniform profile), before the PCM starts to melt ($\beta_{\max}=0$) for the uniform profile and when the PCM has just started melting ($\beta_{\max}=0.03$) for the non-uniform absorber profile. This is undesirable, as it limits the effective use of latent heat storage, the primary function of the system. Notably the $Q_{\text{latent,PCM}}/Q_{\text{stored}}$ ratio is equal to zero for the uniform profile and 0.2 for the non-uniform profile indicating that most of the energy is stored in the form of sensible heat, Figure 7C. For an intermediate band-gap cell ($E_g=0.74$ eV) the production efficiency remains close to 23-24% regardless of the solar absorber heat flux profile, but the system still reaches quasi-steady state conditions within the phase change region melts $\beta_{\max}=0.82$ (uniform profile) and $\beta_{\max}=0.52$ (non-uniform profile). This is a hint that in order to get full potential of the latent heat thermal energy storage system crucible heights smaller than 0.72 m for the specific TPV cells.

A balanced compromise in terms of system production efficiency, $Q_{\text{latent,PCM}}/Q_{\text{stored}}$ ratio, and charging time (t_c) for the realistic absorber profile is a system height of ~ 0.5 m with a band gap equal to 0.74 eV, in which the production efficiency is $\sim 19\%$, the stored latent heat is more than 60% of the overall stored energy and the charging time ~ 10.5 h. At this height, increasing the band gap to 0.9–1.1 eV leads to significant efficiency drops— $\sim 10\%$ at 0.9 eV and $\sim 4\%$ at 1.1 eV—mainly due to a reduced heat extraction from the TPV converter, which becomes comparable to the overall system losses. Although TPV conversion efficiencies are similar for 0.55–0.9 eV, lower band gap cells (0.55-0.74 eV) enhance the TPV heat extraction flux, mitigating the impact of re-emission and lateral system losses, thus improving the net production efficiency. Indicative values for η_{TPV} , values for $H_c \sim 0.48$ m include 39% (0.55 eV), 43% (0.74 eV), 40% (0.90 eV) and 30% (1.1 eV).

By further optimizing the solar absorber, i.e. obtaining a uniform illumination profile, the system can reach production efficiencies close to 27% and a high $Q_{\text{latent,PCM}}/Q_{\text{stored}}$ ratio (~ 0.86), however the charging time is close to 20 hours. Evidently, equilibrated charging-discharging conditions and uniform input profiles can have a positive impact on the system thermal performance in terms of latent heat storage and production efficiency. This is because heat losses are lower compared to the non-uniform profile, which results in high re-emission losses at the solar absorber upper part. However, this leads to slow charging systems, as high Q_{TPV} values slow down the PCM melting rate.

Therefore, if shorter charging times and high storage capacities are prioritized, a suitable alternative is a system of $H_c \sim 0.70$ m with a band gap around 0.90 eV, or the reference configuration ($H_c \sim 0.5$ m, $E_g = 0.74$ eV). Overall, the optimal operating range for Mode C/D lies within $H_c = [0.48-0.72]$ m and $E_g = [0.55-0.74]$ eV. Within this window, taller systems ($H_c > 0.5$ m) require higher band gaps to ensure full PCM melting, while shorter systems benefit from lower band gaps to maintain production efficiencies above 20%.

Mode C

During **Mode C** (charging) the ability of the system to store energy as sensible and latent heat can be reflected by the Stefan number (Ste), which quantifies the sensible to latent heat in the PCM. Another key indicator is the ratio of the energy stored in the PCM, either as latent heat $Q_{\text{latent,PCM}}$ or as both latent and sensible heat $Q_{\text{stored,PCM}}$ to the total energy stored in the system (Q_{stored}). For an effective LH-SISTPV battery operating at ultra-high temperatures, the energy storage in the PCM—particularly as latent heat—should dominate. This not only enhances latent storage efficacy, which is desirable in latent heat energy storage systems, but also helps prevent overheating of the supplementary system components, such as the insulation materials, but also the PCM and its crucible.

The variation of the Stefan number reveals important trends regarding the system heat storage efficacy and its temperature variations. In the case of the uniform absorber profile, numerical results indicate that as the system height increases, the Stefan number decreases, indicating that latent heat storage becomes more dominant at greater heights, Figure 8A. Indicatively for the “re-emission”-“non-adiabatic” case scenario, the Stefan number drops from 0.24 to 0.14 as the system height increases from 0.24 m to 0.72 m. On the contrary, for the non-uniform absorber profile, the Stefan number shows the opposite trend, rising from 0.33 to 0.66 over the same height range. This increase can be attributed to the accumulated heat flux at the upper part of the solar absorber (See Appendix: Figure 23), leading to greater temperature variations and potential overheating risks. The non-uniform profile creates localized regions of higher sensible heat storage, reducing the relative contribution of latent heat and making temperature management more challenging.

The efficacy of latent heat storage can be also assessed by the dimensionless ratio $Q_{\text{latent,PCM}}/Q_{\text{stored}}$, as shown in Figure 8B. For systems with a uniform heat flux profile, this ratio increases with crucible height (for all types of heat flux boundary condition profiles), indicating

that taller systems are more effective at storing energy as latent heat. For instance, under “non-adiabatic” and “re-emission” conditions this ratio increases monotonically from 0.68 to 0.77 for a crucible height within 0.24-0.72 m. In contrast, under a non-uniform heat flux profile, the latent heat contribution decreases until a height of 0.48 m suggesting a shift towards sensible heat dominance in the upper PCM regions, possibly due to a combination of inefficient energy distribution and excess losses. This fact is evident even for the “adiabatic” and “zero re-emission” scenario, in which the $Q_{latent,PCM}/Q_{stored}$ ratio drops from 0.48 to 0.4 for a crucible height increase from 0.24 m to 0.48 m. As height increases to 0.72 m, latent heat storage improves again ($Q_{latent,PCM}/Q_{stored}=0.45$). The same trend is observed also for the “non-adiabatic”, “re-emission scenario”, in which the $Q_{latent,PCM}/Q_{stored}$ ratio takes values of around 0.6 ($H_c=0.24$ m), 0.53 ($H_c=0.48$ m) and 0.57 ($H_c=0.72$ m). This trend highlights the importance of solar absorber illumination profile uniformity in optimizing latent heat storage efficacy, especially when operating under realistic conditions that include losses and re-radiation.

Despite these variations in heat distribution inside the PCM, the $Q_{stored,PCM}/Q_{stored}$ ratio remains nearly constant across the different system heights for the realistic case scenario of “non-adiabatic”, “re-emission” scenario, Figure 8C. In the uniform profile this ratio is within 0.84-0.9, whereas in the non-uniform profile this ratio is slightly lower 0.78-0.81, indicating slightly higher system temperatures in the latter case. The fact that this ratio remains stable suggests that, despite any local temperature fluctuations, the overall energy storage process remains consistent under realistic conditions. However, the slightly elevated $Q_{stored,PCM}/Q_{stored}$ ratio in the non-uniform profile implies that a greater fraction of energy is stored in non-PCM components, potentially reducing the effectiveness of latent heat storage and increasing system temperatures. This highlights once again the importance of maintaining an as uniform as possible heat flux profile in the solar absorber.

Finally, the crucible height highly affects the PCM melting time, Figure 8D. For the non-uniform profile, doubling the crucible height from 0.24 m to 0.48 m the charging time increases almost 2.55 times for all boundary conditions tested and 3.65 times when the crucible height triples from 0.24 m to 0.72 m. For the uniform profile the charging time almost changes monotonically with the crucible height, i.e. doubling the crucible height the charging time doubles and tripling the crucible height increases around 2.9 times.

Figure 8. Mode C: (A) Ste number, (B) $Q_{latent,PCM}/Q_{stored}$ ratio (total latent heat stored in the PCM to the total system energy), (C) $Q_{stored,PCM}/Q_{stored}$ ratio (total energy stored in the PCM, including latent and sensible heat, to the total energy stored in the system), and, (D) t_c vs. H_c and system conditions.

Mode D

During Mode D (discharging), the crucible height influences significantly the system performance and discharging time, especially in the case of high-band gap cells ($E_g > 0.90$) in which the heat extraction (W/cm^2) is low, Figure 9A, B. All cases are compared with the “adiabatic” and “zero re-emission” case in which the maximum thermal discharging efficiency (100 %) and discharging time are expected. Since the volume to TPV surface ratio remains

constant regardless of the crucible height and the extracted height per area remains constant, the PCM discharging time does not depend on the crucible height under adiabatic conditions (dashed line in Figure 9A). For low band gap cells ($E_g \sim 0.55$ eV) heat is extracted at a high pace, i.e. ~ 9 - 10 W/cm² at the beginning of the PCM solidification phenomenon down to ~ 3 W/cm². This is the reason why the Q_{TPV}/Q_{losses} ratio is ~ 5 (See *Heat losses analysis*, Figure 31) for the small crucible height and over 10 for heights $H > 0.48$ m. For such low band gap cells the discharging time is close to the adiabatic case (with a relative error less than 10%) for all heights studied. Notably, for a $H > 0.48$ m the relative difference is less than $\sim 2.6\%$. For a TPV cell with $E_g = 0.74$ eV, it can be observed that a height of at least 0.48 m should be selected in order to achieve discharging times close to the adiabatic conditions. The discharging thermal efficiency is also high for both heights ($\eta_{d,th} \approx 88\%$ % for $H = 0.48$ m and $\eta_{d,th} \approx 92\%$ % for $H = 0.72$ m, Figure 9B, Table 5). For a higher band gap cell of $E_g = 0.90$ eV the system can still operate with a high discharging efficiency if a crucible height of $H > 0.48$ m is chosen. For even higher band gap TPV cells ($E_g = 1.10$ eV), the system highly deviated from the adiabatic conditions and can be operated with a relatively good thermal discharge efficiency (slightly lower than 80%) only if a crucible of at least 0.72 m is chosen. Thus, this type of high-band gap cells is recommended for large-height systems, which, however, require optimized beam-down collectors to achieve uniform absorber heat flux profiles.

Figure 9. Mode D: (A) t_d vs. H_c and E_g (in the graph: solid line: real case, dotted line: adiabatic conditions, Table: t_d deviation of each case from the adiabatic conditions), (B) Efficiency values vs. H_c and E_g (Straight lines upper part of the graph: $\bar{\eta}_{d,th}$, single dots lower part of the graph: $\bar{\eta}_{TPV}$).

Mode S

During **Mode S**, the system storage capacity can reach over ~ 10 hours, ~ 19 hours and ~ 31 hours for a crucible height of 0.24 m, 0.48 m and 0.72 m, respectively. This means that when the system has just melted, it enters into a self-discharging (storage) mode until it loses all of its stored latent heat energy from its surrounding surfaces to the ambient. It must be noted that the thermal insulation method is more relevant for the small-scale system (0.24 m) than for taller crucible heights (0.72 m), where the volume-to-surface area of the whole system increases significantly and, thus, the heat losses from the system surrounding areas to the environment reduce accordingly. This observation is reflected by the storage capacity of the system, which increases as we move to higher scales.

Full cycle: Modes C & D

Numerical results indicate that the system has a high potential of surpassing the round-trip efficiency $\bar{\eta}_{RT}$ of 20% even under realistic operating conditions (i.e. non-uniform solar absorber profile) when the bandgap of the TPV cells is low (< 0.74 eV) and the crucible height is large ($H_c > 0.48$ m), **Figure 10B**. For such a non-uniform solar absorber profile, the round-trip efficiency values for 0.74 eV TPV cells range within ~ 19 - 23% for $H_c = [0.24-0.72]$ m. Further advancements in the solar flux profile and the TPV cell band-gap, which are feasible to be achieved (e.g. rather uniform heat flux profile and utilization of low band-gap TPV cell band) in the future can lead to round-trip efficiencies of over 25%. Indicatively, moving to lower band-gap cells ($E_g = 0.55$ eV) the round-trip efficiency exceeds 20% even for small crucible heights (for instance for $H_c = 0.24$ m the $\bar{\eta}_{RT}$ is $\sim 21\%$), but stays close to this value even for taller crucibles (e.g. $\sim 23\%$ for $H_c = 0.72$ m) owing to excessive re-emission losses from the solar absorber to the ambient. For a uniform profile the $\bar{\eta}_{RT}$ varies within ~ 22 - 26% for $H_c = [0.24-0.72]$ m and $E_g = 0.74$ eV; such round-trip efficiency values are similar for lower band gap cells, as well. This is because the $\bar{\eta}_{TPV}$ and $\bar{\eta}_{d,th}$ values are close for these two types of band-gaps across all crucible heights studied, affecting, the round-trip efficiency, **Table 5**.

In higher band gap cells owing to a slower heat extraction from the TPV cell, the discharge thermal efficiency, $\bar{\eta}_{d,th}$, is negatively affected especially from shorter crucibles. The worst-case scenario is for $H_c = 0.24$ m and $E_g = 1.1$ eV, in which the discharge thermal efficiency is $\sim 50\%$ (signifying excessive lateral losses), followed by $E_g = 0.90$ eV of the same height in which

$\bar{\eta}_{d,th}$ is around 65%. If TPV cells of band gap equal to 0.90 eV are to be used, tall crucible heights (0.72 m) should be used respectively to achieve an acceptable discharge thermal efficiency ($\sim 86\%$) and consequently round-trip efficiency ($\sim 19\%$). In fact, tall crucibles are always preferable regardless of the TPV cell bandgap value. This is attributed to the fact that for the specific design proposed the volume to TPV surface ratio remains constant regardless of the crucible height and the extracted height per area remains constant resulting in almost constant $\bar{\eta}_{TPV}$ values regardless of the system height. This tendency is observed for all TPV cell bandgaps. On the other hand, the ratio of the surfaces that lose thermal energy to the environment (upper and bottom parts of the system) to the overall system volume reduces, leading to an increased $\bar{\eta}_{d,th}$ efficiency as the system height increases.

It should be mentioned that apart from the TPV band gap the solar absorber re-emission losses are still limiting the high potential of this system to reach to round-trip efficiencies of over 40% even for a uniform absorber profile. Such losses in conjunction with the system lateral losses and the solar absorber heat flux profile, affect as well the total round-trip efficiency and charging-discharging time, t_{RT} , in a full cycle. As the system height increases, the deviation of the t_{RT} for the cases on uniform and non-uniform profile becomes more pronounced, **Figure 10A**. Notably there is an inverse correlation between system round-trip efficiency and overall charge-discharge time. For highly efficient systems (for instance of low band-gap cells), in which the t_{RT} is minimized per system height, the $\bar{\eta}_{RT}$ is correspondingly maximized.

Figure 10. Full cycling mode (A) total charging/discharging time, t_{RT} , in a full circle (including pre-heating), and **(B)** Round trip system efficiency, $\bar{\eta}_{TPV}$, for different E_g and H_c .

Numerical results also indicate that the system charging efficiency is significantly affected by the solar absorber re-emission losses and moderately by the crucible height. As shown in Table 4, under ideal conditions, the charging efficiency $\bar{\eta}_c$ keeps an almost constant high value (93-94%) regardless of the crucible height. However, when accounting for re-emission losses, $\bar{\eta}_c$ drops down to 58-68%. This high variation can be primarily attributed to the solar absorber heat flux profile: with a uniform profile, $\bar{\eta}_c$ ranges from 65-68% across the different crucible heights, while with a non-uniform profile lowers to 58-61%.

Table 5. Summary of results for the envisaged system (Modes B, C & D) - Non-Uniform absorber profile (Re-emission and lateral losses are included).

H_c (m)	m_{PCM}/Q_{in} (kg/kW)	E_g (eV)	t_{pr} (h)	t_c (h)	t_d (h)	t_{RT1}^1 (h)	t_{RT2}^2 (h)	t_{stor} (h)	$\bar{\eta}_{abs}$ (%)	$\bar{\eta}_c$ (%)	$\bar{\eta}_{d,el}$ (%)	$\bar{\eta}_{TPV}$ (%)	$\bar{\eta}_{d,th}$ (%)	$\bar{\eta}_{RT}$ (%)
0.24	2.35	0.55	1.13	1.38	2.57	3.95	5.09	-	66.96	60.90	34.02	39.42	86.31	20.72
0.48	5.19	0.55	2.01	3.62	2.75	6.37	8.38	-	64.89	58.10	36.69	39.37	93.19	21.32
0.72	8.02	0.55	3.16	5.13	2.90	8.03	11.19	-	66.07	59.26	37.65	39.41	95.53	22.31
0.24	2.35	0.74	1.13	1.38	3.98	5.36	6.49	-	66.96	60.90	31.65	41.35	76.56	19.28
0.48	5.19	0.74	2.01	3.62	4.51	8.13	10.14	-	64.89	58.10	36.12	41.18	87.70	20.99
0.72	8.02	0.74	3.16	5.13	4.89	10.02	13.18	-	66.07	59.26	37.97	41.35	91.83	22.50
0.24	2.35	0.90	1.13	1.38	5.65	7.03	8.16	-	66.96	60.90	24.18	37.33	64.77	14.73
0.48	5.19	0.90	2.01	3.62	6.90	10.52	12.53	-	64.89	58.10	29.71	37.08	80.13	17.26
0.72	8.02	0.90	3.16	5.13	7.79	12.92	16.08	-	66.07	59.26	32.31	37.37	86.47	19.15
0.24	2.35	1.10	1.13	1.38	7.73	9.11	10.24	-	66.96	60.90	12.81	25.33	50.58	7.80
0.48	5.19	1.10	2.01	3.62	10.43	14.05	16.06	-	64.89	58.10	16.81	24.44	68.78	9.77
0.72	8.02	1.10	3.16	5.13	12.46	17.59	20.75	-	66.07	59.26	19.36	24.90	77.75	11.47
0.24	2.35	-	-	-	-	-	-	9.89	-	-	-	-	-	-
0.48	5.19	-	-	-	-	-	-	18.84	-	-	-	-	-	-
0.72	8.02	-	-	-	-	-	-	30.52	-	-	-	-	-	-

1. Without preheating phase. 2. Including preheating phase.

Notably, for small-scale systems ($H_c < 0.24$ m) the efficiency difference between uniform and non-uniform profiles is only ~6%. However, for larger systems ($H_c > 0.24$ m), the charging efficiency for the non-uniform profile starts to decline due to the increased re-emission losses and the lateral heat losses at the system upper part, deviating by ~13% from the uniform case. For systems of higher height ($H_c \sim 0.72$ m), the charging efficiency begins to recover as the heat losses start to decrease relative to the system volume (See *Heat losses analysis*).

The derived results are of high importance, as they can give as a hint of how to integrate the envisaged system in a future CSP plant. Summary of the charging times, efficiencies and relative differences from the ideal case (Uniform profile with zero absorber and sidewalls losses) can be found in the supportive material (Design effect on the system performance: Table 16, Table 16, Table 17).

Conclusions

We have introduced a novel conceptual design of a LH-SISTPV system operating at temperatures ~1157°C. The system consists of three integrated subsystems: (i) a solar absorber cylindrical cavity as the charging unit, (ii) an InGaAs TPV converter as the discharging unit, and (iii) a FeSiB-based LHTES for storage. Single-junction InGaAs solar cells are promising candidates for LH-SISTPV systems operating at temperatures ~1150-1200°C, where the emitter temperature is dictated by the PCM melting point in the LHTES. A multi-level analysis based on a transient 3D CFD model has shed a light on the thermal losses induced on the thermal energy storage system and on the involved system efficiencies, during its four operating modes, i.e., simultaneous charging/discharging, charging, discharging and storage phases. The solar aperture re-emission losses to the environment have been also accounted for during charging modes. All cases have been compared with three types of non-realistic conditions, i.e. i. uniform absorber heat flux profile, ii. negligible re-emission absorber losses, and, iii. zero system losses to assess the effect of these key parameters on the system performance.

It has been demonstrated that several of the proposed operating/ design principles (e.g., compact system design, movable parts depending on the operating mode) can lead to a highly competitive system of round-trip efficiency over 20% -especially for a system height taller than 0.48 m and lower band gap cells ($E_g \leq 0.74$ eV). Concerning the system losses, it has been demonstrated that the insulating method affects mostly the discharging and storage modes, whereas during the charge-only phase and the simultaneous charge/discharge operation the lateral heat losses play a less important role, at least for the operating /design conditions, if to be compared with the solar aperture losses.

Additionally, by studying several cases of crucible heights within 0.24-0.72 m and TPV cell band-gaps within 0.55-1.1 eV it has been revealed that under the specific operating conditions (~1157°C) the optimum cases in terms of overall system losses, system efficiencies and charging/discharging times are the ones with a system height within 0.48-0.72 m and of band-gap cells around 0.74 eV. Under such technical specifications the system can be successfully integrated into a CSP plant, paving the way for a highly competitive alternative to molten salt-based systems.

Appendix

System simulation

In order to assess the system optothermoelectric performance a computational fluid dynamics (CFD) model is applied in ANSYS Fluent™ platform based on the enthalpy porosity approach^{44,45}, which is a widely used model for solidification-melting problems. In the same platform we couple through in-house user defined functions (UDFs) in C programming language the CFD model with distinct sub-models describing the behaviour of the system sub-components. More specifically, the sub-models solved externally from the CFD model are a) an optical model for the solar absorber heat flux distribution and b) an electric model for the TPV converter efficiency under variable TPV cells band-gaps and emitter temperatures. Additional sub-models are also included in the CFD model as concerns the solar and emitter cavity losses. For instance, the solar absorber re-emission losses are calculated through the net-radiation method. A schematic of the simulating strategy is presented in Figure 11.

Figure 11. LH-SISTPV system simulating strategy.

The multi-physics numerical model used to simulate the phase change process in the LH-SISTPV system has been validated in previous works^{36,46} and is detailed in the *LHTES battery thermal assessment*. In this model, the PCM (FeSiB alloy) liquid fraction (LFR) varies from 0 (solid) to 1 (liquid) during phase change. The system's boundary conditions are defined based on the simulated operating mode (see C.4. BCs summary). In Modes C/D & C (system charging), the entire domain is initially set to 25 °C to simulate first the PCM pre-heating phase. The phase changing phenomenon begins when the temperature inside the crucible reaches the onset melting temperature of the FeSiB alloy ($T_s=1147^\circ\text{C}$) and completes when it exceeds the PCM melting endpoint ($T_l=1167^\circ\text{C}$). The average PCM melting temperature is 1157°C. In Modes D and S (discharging and storage, respectively) the opposite phenomenon occurs, whereas both modes commence immediately after the completion of the melting process. The initial volume-averaged temperature for each modeled sub-component is derived from the numerical results obtained at the end of Mode C. Each solar absorber receives a heat flux of ~10 kW, irrespective of its height, which varies based on the crucible height. Since each solar tube is shared between two crucibles (referred to also as LHTES module, Figure 14), the total heat flux per LHTES module is ~20 kW.

Detailed concept description

The LH-SISTPV system as a whole

The LH-SISTPV system as a whole has been described in detail in the main text (System Design, Geometry and Performance Indicators). The different arrangements corresponding to the four (4) operating modes of the LH-SISTPV system are depicted in Figure 2 (in System Design, Geometry and Performance Indicators) and Figure 12. In the following sub-sections we go through details on the system sub-components (CAD designs and material properties). Further, details of the concept idea can be also found in (Issued Patent Number P202430621)³⁵.

Figure 12. 2D CAD designs of the CSP-LHTPV concept (A) Mode C/D, (B) Mode C, (C) Mode D, and, (D) Mode S. (ZY plane).

System sub-components

This section provides in-detail description of the three (3) main system sub-components, i.e. a) charging system (solar absorber), b) storage system (LHTES system), and c) conversion system (TPV converter), with regard to the four possible operating modes.

Charging system: The charging system is a beam-down CSP design of a cavity receiver with an optical system of radiation collection and distribution, and redirection. First, the solar radiation is collected through a large, circular heliostat field on a hyperboloid mirror suspended high above the centre of the field. From there, a vertical ray (“beam-down”) reaches the ground. Then, the four (4) solar concentrators (CPCs) of each module collect the incoming radiation, and they distribute at the four (4) cylindrical sidewalls of each PCM crucible. Each solar concentrator forms part of two adjacent crucibles, and, thus, the incoming solar radiation per concentrator is split between two crucibles, Figure 13. The system has been designed so that the total incoming concentration flux per solar absorber will be equal to around 10 kW, corresponding to a concentration factor of C~900 suns.

Figure 13. 3D CAD design of the solar absorber/cone.

Some of the basic design specs of the system are also elaborated. More specifically, the solar absorber has been designed to have an inner diameter is approximately 112 mm. Its height will be variable depending on the crucible height. In the reference crucible height, i.e. 0.48 m, the total solar absorber height is 0.48 m, with the 0.46 m of it receiving the solar radiation. Extra radiation is concentrated at its bottom of thickness 0.02 m and of graphite material; this thickness remains constant regardless the studied crucible height, Table 8. The solar cone (CPC), in turn, has an upper (entry) rectangular side of 240x240 mm dimensions and a round bottom (exit) side of a diameter of around 60 mm and a height of approximately 320 mm, corresponding to an acceptance angle of 15°. In terms of materials selection, the solar absorber forms part of the crucible sidewalls and is a non-reflecting piece, i.e. graphite. The cone can be covered additionally with a thin layer of white alumina or any high-temperature resisting metal, whereas it is water cooled. The 3D CAD design of the solar absorber /cone is depicted in Figure 13.

Storage system: The proposed PCM crucible (LHTES module) has a rectangular shape, with inwards round-like corners and is replicated to form the full system, Figure 14. The inner cylindrical corners of the crucible function directly as the solar absorber and the adjacent inner planar surfaces as the thermal emitter. The crucible comprises a refractory material that is manufactured from a refractory ceramic with a high melting point $>2000^{\circ}\text{C}$, high thermal conductivity $>20\text{ W/m}\cdot\text{K}$ and high emissivity >0.8 , such as graphite. In a small scale system, the crucible will have an approximate height of 0.24 m (including the floor) and a wall thickness of 0.020 m. In the envisaged system the crucible height will be up to 1 m. A reference geometry of 0.48 m is set for the simulations containing a PCM mass of $\sim 100\text{ kg}$. For reasons of consistency in the parametric analysis we keep the crucible thickness constant. Furthermore, owing to the geometry double symmetry we model only 1/4 of the domain in order to save-up computational cost.

Figure 14. 3D CAD design of the crucible unit along with the PCM and the modelled unit (1/4 of the crucible domain).

The crucible height can be adjusted to scale-up or scale-down the system. In order to avoid excess lateral losses during its operation, thermal insulation should be used –including a combination of AFM with FSB on its bottom and AFM on its top– to fill the volume between the different components.

The contained PCM will be a Si-B-X alloy. Indicative properties of a Si-B-X alloy, i.e. Fe-26.38Si-9.35B eutetic alloy, are summarised in Table 7. Owing to the PCM high solidification/melting temperatures, i.e., 1157°C , the overall system will perform above 1100°C .

Several design specs of the envisaged system are summarized in Table 8.

Table 6. Thermo-physical properties of FeSiB alloy^{32,33} and thermophysical-optical properties of graphite⁴⁷.

Property	Units	FeSiB alloy	Graphite
		Value	Value
Density, ρ	g/cm^3	5.36	1.73
Melting temperature (onset), T_s	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	1147	-
Melting temperature (endpoint), T_l	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	1167	-
Latent heat of fusion, L	J/g	777	-
Specific heat capacity, C_p (1150 $^{\circ}\text{C}$)	$\text{J}/(\text{kg}\cdot\text{K})$	950	2022
Thermal conductivity, k (1150 $^{\circ}\text{C}$)	$\text{W}/(\text{m}\cdot\text{K})$	30	60
Thermal expansion coefficient, β_{th}	$1/\text{K}$	$1.077 \cdot 10^5$	-
Emissivity, ϵ	(-)	-	1^1

¹ Set for numerical simplification. The real value is approximately equal to 0.8-0.9

Table 7. PCM crucible design properties (1/4 crucible geometry).

Height, H_c (m)	Crucible thickness d_c (m)	Width emitter W_c (m)	Volume PCM V_{PCM} (m^3)	Volume Crucible, V_c (m^3)	Mass PCM m_{PCM} (kg)	Absorber height H_{abs} (m)	Absorber sidewall ¹ A_{abs} (m^2)	TPV emitter A_{em} (m^2)
0.24			0.0022	0.0019	11.80	0.22	0.045	0.030
0.48 (Ref)	0.02	0.15	0.0048	0.0033	25.97	0.46	0.089	0.066
0.72			0.0075	0.0047	40.12	0.70	0.133	0.102

¹ Including the bottom wall

Conversion system: The TPV conversion system is a solid-state device designed to convert the stored thermal energy in the PCM into electricity. It consists of an incandescent TPV emitter and TPV cells mounted on a movable TPV holder. The emitter is formed by the inner walls of the graphite crucible, which reaches temperatures close to the FeSiB alloy melting point ($\sim 1157^\circ\text{C}$), radiating heat. The TPV cells, based on InGaAs technology, are positioned in close proximity to the emitter—less than 100 microns—to maximize energy absorption. The TPV holder allows the cells to be either patched or dispatched from the system, depending on the operating mode. When patched, the cells absorb the thermal radiation and generate electrical power. When dispatched, a cavity is formed, and in order to prevent radiative losses through the TPV holder, an insulation layer of AFM, approximately 0.02 m thick, is incorporated at the upper part of the TPV holder. AFM is chosen because of its high melting point in permanent applications, i.e. 1600-1650 $^\circ\text{C}$ ⁴⁸. In order to further minimize radiative losses, the upper part of the insulating material of the TPV holder is lined with a reflective material (i.e. a thin tungsten layer of 1 mm), which redirects the emitted radiation back into the cavity. To prevent overheating and maintain optimal performance, the inner surface of the TPV holder, which faces the TPV cells, is actively water-cooled (e.g. with heat pipes). This cooling mechanism is essential for sustaining the efficiency the TPV cells and prevent their thermal cracking, ensuring stable operation under ultra-high temperature conditions.

Figure 15. TPV converter and TPV holder.

System insulation: Supplementary to the main system components, insulation materials are included at the system upper and bottom surfaces to avoid excess thermal losses to the environment. Following previous analysis for the same and similar systems studied by our research group^{49,50}, alumina fiber mat is used as the most optimum option at most of the system surfaces, i.e. system upper part, TPV holder upper part and system bottom part, insulating material of the solar absorber. However, in the LHTES bottom part an extra layer of fumed silica board (FSB) of is also used in order to further eliminate the system lateral losses.

Table 8. Insulation materials properties (1/4 crucible geometry).

Height, H_c (m)	Upper Section, AFM (m^3)	Bottom Section, AFM/FSB ¹ (m^3)	Insulator of solar absorber ² , AFM (m^3)	AFM $k^{40,48}$, W/mK	FSB k^{40} , W/mK	$T_{melting}$ point AFM ⁴⁰ , $^\circ\text{C}$	$T_{melting}$ point FSB ⁴⁰ , $^\circ\text{C}$
0.24			2.53e-03				
0.48	0.00532	1.56e-03/ 3.35e-04	5.06e-03	0.23 at 120 $^\circ\text{C}$	0.034 at 600 $^\circ\text{C}$	1650	1000
0.72			7.59e-03				

¹For 0.08 m of AFM: Alumina mat by Zircar Ceramics (USA) and 0.02 m of FSB: WDS ultra by Morgan Advanced Materials (UK) ²Modes D and S

System simulation

This sub-section presents in short, the i. optical model for the charging system, ii. the electric model for the TPV converter and iii. the multi-physics model for the LHTPV battery. The latter integrates all sub-models within the same platform, i.e. ANSYS Fluent™.

Beam-down concentrator optical analysis

The optical design of a secondary concentrator (Compound parabolic concentrator - CPC) is a straight forward process, depending on the size of the inlet aperture, the outlet aperture, and the required acceptance angle. In most cases, the resulting length can be truncated up to 50% without significant performance loss. The secondary concentrator of the specific concept requires a square entry aperture for a higher efficiency. Thus, two profiles have to be determined, the one in the flat side of the CPC aperture and the one at the corner, Figure 16. The solar absorber tube is divided into 42 rings across its height (40 of equal height at the sidewalls, i.e. 1-40, and two more at its bottom, i.e. 41 and 42). Each ring is divided into 8 small segments, four of which correspond to the flat side of the CPC (G1, G3, G5, G7) and four at the corner part of CPC aperture (G2, G4, G6, G8).

Optical analysis for this geometry was performed by Monte Carlo ray-tracing calculations using the commercial ray-tracing software TracePRO⁵¹. In the specific analysis, a simplified radiation source has been used, emulating the extension of the hyperboloid top mirror and including mirror errors as well as incomplete land use of the heliostat field. Based on the model, an incident radiative flux profile is calculated, which does not consider re-emission losses. Such losses are then calculated in the CFD model through the net-radiation method, through an iterative process per time step of calculation.

Figure 16. Shape of a secondary concentrator element attached to an absorber tube (optimized for a Beam Down system).

The solar flux on the wall of the absorber tube is shown in Figure 17A. As can be noticed from the profile, the absorber of the beam down system receives more radiation on the side walls, and especially at the upper part close to the ambient, and less on the bottom of the tube. This is an expected result, because secondary concentrators tend to “open” or “widen” the solar beam substantially. This profile, is also almost uniform at each ring, so in the CFD model the average value of this profile is used per ring, Figure 17B. If we observe more carefully the optical results, Figure 17C, there are some local spots of higher flux values per segment, but for this specific analysis we will use the average flux profile per ring. This profile is integrated into the CFD model through polynomial functions (See *Optical model polynomial functions*).

Figure 17. (A) Solar flux profile by ray-tracing simulations, (B) Average profile included in CFD model and (C) example of results of simulations in the absorber sidewalls (Ring 3) and bottom (Rings 41 and 42).

TPV emitter electric model

A steady-state OD electric model for the TPV converter based on the detailed balance theory is solved in MatlabTM programming language. This model has been retrieved by a previous analysis of our research group²⁰ and assumes only radiative recombination in the TPV cells. Therefore, results represent the upper bounds for efficiency (and power density), Figure 18A. The TPV efficiency in this model is defined as the ratio of the electric power produced by the TPV cells (P_{EL}) to the net thermal power outgoing from the side of the emitter facing the cells (Q_{TPV}). Results have been also compared with in-house experiment for 0.9 eV band-gap cells. As can be noticed from Figure 18A, numerical results are close to the experimental for our operating conditions, i.e. emitter temperature $T_{TPV,em} < 1300$ °C.

Figure 18. (A) TPV conversion efficiency η_{TPV} and (B) net extracted heat flux from the TPV emitter, Q_{TPV} .

This model is solved numerically and then results concerning the net heat flux from the emitter with regard its temperature (Q_{TPV} vs. $T_{TPV,em}$), Figure 18B, are incorporated through polynomial functions by means of C Programming language in FluentTM platform. Such functions are used as a boundary condition in the TPV emitter during discharging modes (C/D and D).

LHTES battery thermal assessment

The numerical model utilised to simulate the PCM transition from solid to liquid phase and vice versa is based on the enthalpy porosity approach by Voller⁴⁵ available in FluentTM platform. In this method, the PCM liquid fraction, varying from 0 (solid) to 1 (liquid) is calculated based on the energy equation and thus, the melting front (phase change transition) is almost linearly dependent on the temperature distribution. A mushy region is defined, which represents the phase change transition commonly found in eutetic PCMs and is treated as a ‘pseudo’ porous medium. In reality, the region is a porous layer of partially solidified regions formed during the PCM solidification, usually resembling to dendritic crystals, with liquid among their interstices. The effect of such structures on the PCM melting is of high importance and their presence (if any) is implicitly modelled through a dimensionless parameter called as mushy zone parameter, which is set equal to $A_{mush} = 5 \cdot 10^5$ during melting³⁶, and equal to 10^8 during solidification phase⁴⁶.

The main assumptions that are considered during calculation process are as follows:

- Transient fluid flow and heat transfer mechanisms.
- 3D domain with a double symmetry.

- The flow is considered laminar, due to low Reynolds numbers.
- Inclusion of gravitational force and buoyancy driven natural convection.
- The PCM density and, thus, its volume does not change during its phase change from solid to liquid and vice versa.
- Temperature-dependent specific heat capacity and thermal conductivity values of the eutectic FeSiB alloy.
- The thermal insulations and crucible thermal conductivities are considered as temperature dependent.
- The effect of contact thermal resistance between the PCM and the wall is not considered.
- The outlet system temperature is assumed equal to 27 °C as a worst case scenario.

C.1. Modelled geometry and mesh layout

The investigated geometries, Figures 19A and B, are created in ANSYS DesignModeler. In each case, only the height of the crucible is altered, keeping the rest of the sections at the same dimensions. Furthermore, ¼ of the domain is being simulated in order to reduce the computational cost, owing to the double symmetry of the crucible. For the CFD model, a fixed hybrid grid consisting of tetrahedral cells at the system upper insulation layer and of quadrilateral cells at the rest of the domains is constructed in ANSYS Meshing component, Figure 19C. For each design studied, the same grid density has been used, resulting in a hybrid grid of 293022, 303643, 498126 for modes C/D and C for the heights of 0.24, 0.48 and 0.72 meters, respectively. For modes D and S, in which an extra section is modelled (inner insulation layer), the grid for each height is respectively 310158, 347803, 587214. The most critical domain in terms of grid influence, is the PCM domain, in which the solidification-melting problem is modelled. In this section a grid size of 0.003 m is used.

Figure 19. (A) Modelled geometry in 2D and 3D isometric view of the different modes, (B) Simulated designs and (C) Used numerical grid.

C.2. TPV cavity simulation

This section provides analysis of the several boundary conditions set at the surfaces close to the TPV emitter cavity during the different modes of operations.

Modes C and S: Surface 3: During modes C and S (Charging and Storage) the TPV is retracted from the system. Heat is radiated from the emitter sidewalls to the TPV cavity. Thus, several boundary conditions are set to the system sidewalls.

The radiative heat emitted by surfaces 1 and 2 (upper and bottom surfaces of the TPV cavity) and absorbed by surface 3 (TPV emitter) is equal as (For information, please look at TPV emitter losses and Figure 20A):

$$Q_{TPV,emit(1-3)} = \varepsilon_t \sigma (T_{aver(1)}^4) F_{1-3} A_1 \text{ or} \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

$$Q_{TPV,emit(2-3)} = \varepsilon_t \sigma (T_{aver(2)}^4) F_{2-3} A_2$$

Thus, the net radiative heat transfer in Watts between the two surfaces is equal to:

$$Q_{TPV,net(1,3)} = \varepsilon_t \sigma (T_{aver(3)}^4 - T_{aver(1)}^4) A_1 (1 - F_{1-2}) \text{ or} \quad \text{Equation 2}$$

$$Q_{TPV,net(1,2)} = \varepsilon_t \sigma (T_{aver(3)}^4 - T_{aver(2)}^4) A_2 (1 - F_{2-1})$$

The overall energy loss from TPV emitter surface (3) is equal as:

$$Q_{TPV} = Q_{TPV,net(1,3)} + Q_{TPV,net(1,2)} \quad \text{Equation 3}$$

The temperature at the TPV holder upper part (surface 1) can be calculated by using the simple conduction equation, by assuming at the rear side (surface 6) a temperature of 300 K, a thickness of 0.02 m of the extra insulation material and thermal conductivity of AFM.

For the losses towards the system upper part (from surface 2 towards the environment) an equivalent thickness of 0.02 m is considered, a temperature at the concentrator surface of 300 K and an 1D flow of the heat from surface 2 towards the environment. It should be mentioned that this approach is more accurate for uniform temperature profiles at the TPV emitter surface. As seen from the results (See Figure 31 in Temperature uniformity index), generally the temperature is "rather" uniform at the TPV emitter surface, with a small non-uniformity observed at the PCM preheating phase for crucibles with a height over 0.48 m heated under non-uniform heat flux conditions. Even still, as soon as the PCM phase change phenomenon initiates the temperature tends to homogenize.

Table 9. Cavity properties.

Property	Value	Units
Emissivity graphite, ε_g	1	(-)
Emissivity tungsten, ε_t	$\sim 0.08^{52}$	(-)
Holder surface (top/bottom) $A_{holder (bottom, top)}$	0.0227	m ²
Holder surface (sidewalls) $A_{holder (side)}$	0.1325	m ²

Surface 5: In this surface we assume an effective emissivity of 0.1 (between the emissivity of AFM (or FSB) and Tungsten) and a temperature inside the TPV holder of 300 K.

Surface 4: Since the system upper part is covered with insulation material we consider an adiabatic condition at this surface, as an assumption.

Modes C/D and C (Figure 20B): Surface 3: When the TPV holder is patched to the system, we start producing electricity. The efficiency of the TPV generator is highly dependent on the bandgap of the TPV cells. We are testing for different cases of TPV cells of bandgaps of 0.55, 0.74, 0.9 and 1.1 eV. For each case, the Q_{TPV} is retracted from the TPV surface (surface 3). A polynomial function is used per case, of $Q_{TPV} = f(T_{emitter} = T_3)$. More information on the model used to extract these functions and the polynomial functions used per case can be found in TPV emitter model.

For surfaces 4 and 5, similar boundary conditions are assumed as in Modes B and D.

Figure 20. TPV BCs definition when the TPV holder is (A) retracted (Mode C and S) and (B) patched to the system (Mode C/D and D) – real vs. simulated domain.

C.3. Cavity receiver simulation

This section provides analysis of the several boundary conditions set at the surfaces close to the solar cavity during the different modes of operations.

Modes C/D and C: During Modes C/D and C the LHTES system is patched to the CPC and dispatched from the insulating material at its bottom having its interior absorber (surfaces 7 and 8) uncovered in order to receive the concentrated solar energy. At these surfaces a BC of a heat flux profile is set based on the optical model described in Beam-down concentrator optical analysis. Extra emission losses and re-emission inside the cavity are calculated based on the net-radiation model calculated iteratively at each time step, as described in Net-radiation model in solar cavity.

Figure 21. BCs definition near the solar absorber when the solar concentrator is patched (A) Mode C/D and C and (B) dispatched from the system (Mode D and S) – real vs. simulated domain.

The CPC is water cooled at an average temperature of 300 K (surface 9). The upper surface of the upper insulating material is exposed to environment (surface 10) and, thus, a combination of convective and radiative heat transfer is set with an ambient temperature of 300 K. At the bottom surface of the insulating material (surface 13) a temperature of 300 K is set. The movable insulating material is not simulated fully, so in order to account for the extra insulation surface 12 an 1D conduction equation is solved, by considering a temperature of 300 K at surface 14.

Modes D and S: During modes D and S the LHTES system is retracted from the CPC, moving downwards so that the insulation material along with the bottom of the solar absorber fill in the gap inside the solar cavity (surface 7) to avoid re-emission losses from the cavity.

C.4. BCs summary

This section summarizes the used BCs for each operating mode:

Surface	Mode	BC	Definition	Mode	BC	Definition
3	C, S	Heat flux (UDF)	TPV losses	C/D, D	Heat flux (UDF)	TPV emission
4	C, S	Heat flux	Adiabatic	C/D, D	Heat flux	Adiabatic
5	C, S	Temperature	T=300 K, $\epsilon_{\text{eff}}=0.1$	C/D, D	Temperature	T=300 K, $\epsilon_{\text{eff}}=0.1$
7	C/D, C	Heat flux (UDF)	Solar cavity	D, S	Interior surface	
8	C/D, C	Heat flux (UDF)	Solar cavity	D, S	Temperature	T=300 K, $\epsilon=1$
9	C/D, C	Temperature	T = 300 K	D, S	Temperature	T = 300 K, $\epsilon=0.5$
10	C/D, C	Temperature	T = 300 K, h=30 W/m ² K, $\epsilon=0.5$	D, S	Temperature	T = 300 K, h=30 W/m ² K, $\epsilon=0.5$
11	C/D, C	Heat flux	Adiabatic	D, S	Heat flux	Adiabatic
12	C/D, C	Heat flux (UDF)	1D conduction	D, S	Temperature	T=300 K
13	C/D, C	Temperature	T=300 K	D, S	Temperature	T=300 K
14	C/D, C		Symmetry	D, S		Symmetry
15	C/D, C		Symmetry	D, S		Symmetry

C.5. Numerical set-up

Transient calculations are performed using the commercial software ANSYS Fluent v.22R2. The time step size is set so the Courant number is ~ 0.20 . For the time discretization, a bounded second order implicit scheme is adopted. As concerns the spatial discretization of the equations, the Quick scheme is applied for the solution of the momentum and energy equations, and the PRESTO! Scheme for the pressure equation. Finally, for the velocity-pressure coupling the Coupled Scheme is applied. Similar numerical schemes have been used in previous works^{36,37} after having done a sensitivity analysis of the effect of the different discretization schemes. The net-radiation method, along with the TPV conversion efficiency polynomial functions are incorporated into the model through a user-defined function (UDF) and they are solved iteratively at each computational step. Additional UDFs are utilized for setting the temperature varying material properties.

C.6. Summary of simulated cases

A set of different 73 cases has been simulated to test the system performance under varying critical conditions. The current sub-section provides a summary of the simulated cases.

Table 10. Summary of simulated cases of the envisaged system.

Cases	Operating mode	Absorber profile	Losses abs	Lateral losses	TPV E_g (eV)	Crucible H_c (m)
1-8	C/D	<i>Non-Uniform</i>	v	v	0.55, 0.74, 0.90 , 1.10	0.24
		<i>Uniform</i>	v	v	0.55, 0.74, 0.90 , 1.10	
9-16		<i>Non-Uniform</i>	v	v	0.55, 0.74, 0.90 , 1.10	0.48
		<i>Uniform</i>	v	v	0.55, 0.74, 0.90 , 1.10	
17-20		<i>Non-Uniform</i>	x	v, x	0.74	0.72
		<i>Uniform</i>	x	v, x		
21-28	C	<i>Non-Uniform</i>	v	v	0.55, 0.74, 0.90 , 1.10	0.24
		<i>Uniform</i>	v	v	0.55, 0.74, 0.90 , 1.10	
29-34	C	<i>Non-Uniform</i>	v	v	-	0.48
35-40		<i>Uniform</i>	x	v, x	-	0.72
41-46						0.24
47-54	D	-	-	v	0.55, 0.74, 0.90 , 1.10	0.48
55-62				x	0.55, 0.74, 0.90 , 1.10	0.72
63-70						0.24
71	S	-	-	v	-	0.48
72						0.72
73						

¹Deviation of charging time t_c of the non-uniform profile from the uniform profile.

Sub-models' integration into the CFD model

A supplementary theoretical analysis is provided, in order to demonstrate how we handle the (i) solar input flux profile from the optical model (*Optical model polynomial functions*) and then (ii) the re-emission losses of the solar absorber (*Net-radiation model in solar cavity*) during charging Modes C/D and C. As concerns the TPV cavity, we provide information on (iii) the TPV emitter losses (*TPV emitter losses*), when the TPV cells are retracted from the LHTES system (Modes C and S), and, (iv) the TPV production efficiency quantification, when the TPV generator is operating (Modes C/D and D).

Optical model polynomial functions

Based on the results of the applied optical model, the following polynomial functions of $Q_{in}=f(z)$ are set in Fluent, where z is the z coordinate at the solar absorber surface (or surface 3) and Q_{in} is the input solar flux in W/m^2 . Re-emission losses and redistribution of the solar flux inside the cavity are then iteratively calculated within the CFD model through the net-radiation model.

$$Q_{in} = a_0 + a_1z + a_2z^2 + a_3z^3 + a_4z^4 \quad \text{Equation 4}$$

Table 11. Polynomial functions of $Q_{in}=f(z)$.

Height range	a_0	a_1	a_2	a_3	a_4
0-0.066	-4.2369E+04	1.0034E+05	-5.9085E+04	0	0
0.066-0.48	-3.0613E+04	1.5588E+05	-2.9198E+05	2.3666E+05	-6.9056E+04
0.48-0.87	1.6547E+00	-2.6540E+01	1.9978E+02	-5.1876E+02	5.0601E+02

Net-radiation model in solar cavity

In the net-radiation model⁵³, the net heat flux at a surface (the energy added to a surface k : 7 or 8 in our case) is the difference between the outgoing J_k and incident radiation G_k :

$$Q_{k.net} = J_k - G_k \quad \text{Equation 5}$$

The outgoing flux J_k is the sum of the emitted flux leaving a surface k plus that portion of the incident flux that is reflected from that surface:

$$J_k = \varepsilon_k \sigma T_k^4 + (1 - \varepsilon_k) G_k \quad \text{Equation 6}$$

In this model, we have two surfaces in the enclosure, the solar absorber sidewalls (7) and the solar absorber bottom wall (8). Furthermore, both surfaces emit to the upper part that is exposed to the environment (6). For a higher accuracy the solar absorber cavity is divided into N rings of dh_i height, i.e. into N surfaces. Thus, in total the participating surfaces in the net-radiation model are $N+1$. For each ring we assume uniform properties, i.e. temperature, material properties. The highest the number of rings considered the highest the accuracy of the net-radiation model, especially as concerns the re-emission losses for a non-uniform heat flux profile. However, since this model is solved per each iteration along with the CFD model, increasing the number of rings, increases the computational cost. Following a preliminary analysis and taking into account both accuracy and efficiency, we assume a number of 20

divisions for the reference case of 0.48 m, 10 for the case of 0.24 m and 30 for the case of 0.72 m.

In the net-radiation model, several types of heat fluxes are calculated per N number of divisions in the solar absorber sidewalls and the solar absorber bottom part.

Table 12. Heat flux streams calculated for the net-radiation method.

Absorber Section	Q_{in}	$Q_{abs,losses}$	$Q_{abs,side-bottom} / Q_{abs,bottom-side}$	$Q_{abs,side-side}$	
Sidewalls	$Q_{in,side} (z)^1$	$Q_{o,side-top} [N]$ (Q_{7-6})	$Q_{o,side-bottom} [N]$ (Q_{7-8})	$Q_{i,bottom-side} [N]$ (Q_{8-7})	$Q_{o,side-side} [N, N] \rightarrow$ $Q_{i,side-side} [N, N] \rightarrow$ $Q_{side-side,new} [N]$ (Q_{7-7})
Bottom	$Q_{in,bottom}$	$Q_{o,bottom-top}$ (Q_{8-6})	$Q_{i,side-bottom,ave}$ (Q_{7-8})	$Q_{o,bottom-side} [N]$ (Q_{8-7})	0 (Q_{8-8})
$Q_{in,abs,net} = Q_{in,side} (z) - Q_{o,side-top} [N] - Q_{o,side-bottom} [N] + Q_{i,bottom-side} [N] + Q_{side-side,new} [N]$					

¹ Taken from Table 12

In order to calculate the fluxes in Table 13 the view factors are calculated per surface. The view factor in surface 8 F_{8-8} is equal to zero because it is a planar surface, whereas the F_{7-7} view factor is non-zero since the surface is concave re-emitting to itself.

Table 13. View Factors Calculations (for the different heights tested).

Height H_{abs} (m)	F_{7-8}	F_{7-6}	F_{6-7}	F_{8-7}	F_{8-6}	F_{6-8}	F_{7-7}	F_{8-8}
0.22	0.1275	0.1275	0.935	0.935	0.065	0.065	0.745	0
0.46 (Ref)	0.064	0.064	0.984	0.984	0.017	0.017	0.872	0
0.70	0.043	0.043	0.993	0.993	0.007	0.007	0.915	0

The model redistributes the radiative energy among the surfaces ensuring that the net heat flux at each point is a result of multiple interactions, shaping, thus, the thermal behavior of the absorber cavity, Figure 22, Figure 23.

Figure 22. Heat flux contours of (A) the solar flux profile, Q_{in} and (B) the re-emission losses to the environment, $Q_{abs,losses}$ (for a $\beta=0.5$).

Figure 23. Heat flux contours of the net heat flux profile at the storage system sidewalls, $Q_{in,abs,net}$ (for a $\beta=0.5$).

TPV emitter losses

In order to calculate the emission losses, $Q_{TPV,loss}$ from the crucible sidewalls (3) towards the bottom (1) and (2) upper part the following equation is used:

$$Q_{TPV,emit(3-1)} = \varepsilon_1 \varepsilon_3 \sigma (T_{aver(3)})^4 F_{3-1} A_3 \quad \text{or} \quad \text{Equation 7}$$

$$Q_{TPV,emit(3-2)} = \varepsilon_2 \varepsilon_3 \sigma (T_{aver(3)})^4 F_{3-2} A_3$$

, by assuming the graphite emissivity is close to 1 and $\varepsilon_{1,2} = \varepsilon_t$ whis equation simplifies to

$$Q_{TPV,emit(3-1)} = \varepsilon_t \sigma (T_{aver(3)})^4 F_{3-1} A_3 \quad \text{or} \quad \text{Equation 8}$$

$$Q_{TPV,emit(3-2)} = \varepsilon_t \sigma (T_{aver(3)})^4 F_{3-2} A_3$$

Inside the cavity the different view factors sum up to unity as follows:

$$F_{3-3} + F_{3-2} + F_{3-1} = 1 \quad \text{Equation 9}$$

$$F_{1-3} + F_{1-2} = 1 \rightarrow F_{1-3} = 1 - F_{1-2} \quad \text{Equation 10}$$

$$F_{2-1} + F_{2-3} = 1 \rightarrow F_{2-3} = 1 - F_{2-1} \quad \text{Equation 11}$$

The view factor of two parallel plates based on⁵³ is approximated as:

$$F_{1-2} = \frac{2}{\pi XY} \ln \left[\frac{(1+X^2)(1+Y^2)}{1+X^2+Y^2} \right]^{1/2} + X\sqrt{1+Y^2} \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{X}{\sqrt{1+Y^2}} \right) \quad \text{Equation 12}$$

$$+ Y\sqrt{1+X^2} \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{Y}{\sqrt{1+X^2}} \right) - X \tan^{-1} X - Y \tan^{-1} Y$$

, with $F_{2-1} = F_{1-2}$ Equation 13

Finally, we apply the reciprocity relation to calculate the rest of the view factors inside the cavity:

$$A_3 F_{3-1} = A_1 F_{1-3} \rightarrow F_{3-1} = \frac{A_1}{A_3} F_{1-3} = \frac{A_1}{A_3} (1 - F_{1-2}) \quad \text{Equation 14}$$

$$A_2 F_{2-1} = A_1 F_{1-2} \quad \text{Equation 15}$$

Finally, Equation 8 can be rewritten as:

$$Q_{TPV,emit(3-1)} = \varepsilon_t \sigma (T_{aver(3)})^4 A_1 (1 - F_{1-2}) \quad \text{or} \quad \text{Equation 16}$$

$$Q_{TPV,emit(3-2)} = \varepsilon_t \sigma (T_{aver(3)})^4 A_2 (1 - F_{2-1})$$

TPV emitter model polynomial functions

Based on the results of the applied TPV model, the following polynomial functions of $Q_{TPV,net} = f(T_{TPV,em})$ are set in Fluent, where $T_{TPV,em}$ is the temperature at the TPV emitter surface (or surface 3) and $Q_{TPV,net}$ is the overall emitted thermal heat from the TPV emitter by taking into account both the conversion efficiency of the TPV cell and reemission of thermal radiation from the TPV cell to the TPV emitter:

For $T_{TPV,em} < 1270$ K

$$Q_{TPV,net} = a_0 + a_1 T_{TPV,em} + a_2 T_{TPV,em}^2 + a_3 T_{TPV,em}^3 + a_4 T_{TPV,em}^4 \quad \text{Equation 17}$$

For 1270 K $< T_{TPV,em} < 2000$ K

$$Q_{TPV,net} = b_0 + b_1 T_{TPV,em} + b_2 T_{TPV,em}^2 + b_3 T_{TPV,em}^3 + b_4 T_{TPV,em}^4 \quad \text{Equation 18}$$

Figure 24. Polynomial constants used in the TPV emitter model integrated into the CFD model.

Case	a_0	a_1	a_2	a_3	a_4	$T_{TPV,em} < 1270$ K
0.55	-1.1855E+00	2.0204E-03	4.3641E-06	-1.1954E-08	7.3577E-12	
0.74	3.4657E+00	-1.7211E-02	3.2760E-05	-2.8437E-08	9.6508E-12	
0.9	5.1279E+00	-2.2666E-02	3.8022E-05	-2.8795E-08	8.4554E-12	
1.1	-3.9156 E+00	1.2194E-02	-1.2724E-05	4.5652E-09	0	
Case	b_0	b_1	b_2	b_3	b_4	$1270 < T_{TPV,em} < 2000$ K
0.55	-4.9046E+01	1.1995E-01	-1.0563E-04	3.4177E-08	0	
0.74	-6.6578E+01	1.5247E-01	-1.2187E-04	3.4468E-08	0	
0.9	-7.4114E+01	1.6138E-01	-1.2091E-04	3.1520E-08	0	
1.1	-6.8099E+01	1.4188E-01	-1.0065E-04	2.4576E-08	0	

Supplementary results

Heat losses analysis

This sub-section provides supplementary results on the heat losses in three main operating modes (Mode C/D, C and S).

Mode C/D

The following figures present time-varying results of the lateral heat losses (Figure 25), the solar absorber re-emission losses (Figure 26), and the power production Figure 27. The solid lines present results of the non-uniform absorber profile and the dotted lines of the uniform absorber profile.

Notably the lateral system losses (in kW/m^2) exhibit a relatively little variation with the LHTES height, whereas the solar absorber re-emission losses show a significant decrease as the system height increases.

Figure 25. \dot{Q}_{losses} (kW/m^2) with time for H_C : (A) 0.24 m, (B) 0.46 m and (C) 0.72 m.

Figure 26. $\dot{Q}_{abs,losses}$ (kW/m^2) with time for H_C : (A) 0.24 m, (B) 0.46 m and (C) 0.72 m.

Figure 27. η_{prod} (%) with time for H_C : (A) 0.24 m, (B) 0.46 m and (C) 0.72 m.

Mode C

This sub-section summarizes results of the time-dependent lateral losses \dot{Q}_{losses} per unit area of the lateral surfaces (TPV, LHTES bottom and upper part) for all tested heights, Figure 28A. Additionally, it presents the time-dependent absorber losses $\dot{Q}_{abs,losses}$, per unit absorber area across different system heights, Figure 28B. Finally, the time-varying absorber (Figure 28C) and charging efficiencies (Figure 28D) are presented.

It is demonstrated, that the lateral losses per unit area tend to decrease as the system height increases, proving the high advantage of the arrangement proposed in terms of scalability. A similar trend is observed for the overall absorber losses, for both the uniform and the non-uniform solar flux profiles. In terms of system efficiencies, it can be observed that as the system height increases, the divergence in η_c and η_{abs} between the realistic "non-uniform" heat flux

profile and the ideal "uniform" profile increases accordingly, Figure 28C and D. This can be primarily attributed to the absorber losses, which are higher for the non-uniform profile compared to the uniform profile. In terms of system lateral losses, both profiles lead to similar results. Thus, while lateral losses are primarily influenced by the system height, the absorber losses are determined by both the system height and the solar flux profile.

Figure 28. (A) \dot{Q}_{losses} (kW/m²), (B) $\dot{Q}_{abs,losses}$ (kW/m²), (C) η_{abs} and (D) η_c with time (dotted line: uniform profile, solid line: non-uniform profile)

Mode C

Figure 29. (A) \dot{Q}_{TPV} (W/cm²) and (B) $\dot{Q}_{TPV}/\dot{Q}_{losses}$ ratio with time for $H_c = (0.24-0.72$ m) and $E_g = (0.55-1.1$ eV).

This sub-section summarizes results of the time-varying extracted net heat \dot{Q}_{TPV} per area of the TPV emitter for all tested heights and band gaps, Figure 30A. Additionally, it presents the time-dependent \dot{Q}_{TPV} to \dot{Q}_{losses} ratio, providing insight into the proportion of useful extracted heat relative to heat lost to the environment, Figure 30B. Notably, the $\dot{Q}_{TPV}/\dot{Q}_{losses}$ ratio increases with both larger LHTPV battery scales and lower band-gap cells. This results in a twofold benefit: low-band gap cells enable rapid heat extraction from the TPV emitter around 1100-1200°C of operation, while scaling-up the system reduces the surface-to-volume ratio, thereby minimizing lateral heat losses. Based on these findings, an effective system operation can be achieved for crucible heights exceeding 0.48 m and for TPV cell band gaps of below 0.75 eV. The time-varying P_{el} profile follows almost the same trend with the \dot{Q}_{TPV} profile, signifying an almost constant η_{TPV} value for each studied case, Figure 30C.

Design effect on the system performance

This sub-section presents a summary of global critical variables describing the envisaged system under all operating modes.

Mode C/D: A summary of the results for the envisaged system, such as preheating/charging time, time to reach quasi-steady state conditions, and conversion efficiency of the solar absorber and the whole system is presented in Table 15.

Table 14. Summary of results for the envisaged system (Mode C/D).

Case	Heat flux profile	Losses abs/ Lateral	Crucible H_c (m)	TPV E_g (eV)	t_{pr} (h)	t_c (h)	t_{eq} (h)	$Q_{abs.}$ losses (MJ)	Q_{losses} (MJ)	Q_{in} (MJ)	Q_{TPV} (MJ)	P_{el} (MJ)	η_{abs} (%)	η_c (%)	η_{TPV} (%)	η_{prod} (%)	$\eta_{prod, total}$ (%)	β_{max} (-)
1	Non-Uniform	v	0.24	0.55	1.30	2.79	5.19	-15.56	-2.27	50.52	-19.86	-7.92	69.20	64.71	39.88	15.67	14.06	1
2				0.74	1.20	1.83	5.01	-10.58	-1.52	33.20	-7.07	-3.06	68.14	63.57	43.23	9.21	10.85	1
3				0.90	1.16	1.59	5.05	-9.34	-1.33	28.80	-3.52	-1.43	67.56	62.95	40.60	4.97	8.06	1
4				1.10	1.13	1.48	5.50	-8.80	-1.24	26.81	-1.77	-0.53	67.17	62.55	30.26	1.99	5.36	1
5				0.55	1.33	2.15	5.09	-10.60	-1.73	38.96	-14.73	-5.86	72.80	68.36	39.78	15.04	14.03	1
6				0.74	1.25	1.49	4.87	-7.62	-1.22	26.96	-5.55	-2.39	71.73	67.21	43.07	8.88	11.15	1
7	Uniform	v	0.24	0.90	1.21	1.31	5.05	-6.82	-1.08	23.71	-2.80	-1.13	71.23	66.67	40.27	4.76	8.60	1
8				1.10	1.18	1.22	5.21	-6.45	-1.02	22.16	-1.41	-0.42	70.91	66.32	29.74	1.90	5.44	1
9				0.55	2.53	8.36	10.89	-41.75	-5.79	151.37	-91.35	-35.56	72.42	68.59	38.93	23.49	19.10	0.30
10	Non-Uniform	v	0.48	0.74	2.24	10.53	14.16	-64.24	-8.63	190.69	-85.63	-36.89	66.31	61.79	43.08	19.34	17.03	1
11				0.90	2.14	5.35	10.54	-33.15	-4.36	96.93	-24.58	-9.91	65.80	61.30	40.30	10.22	10.96	1
12				1.10	2.01	4.27	10.55	-26.87	-3.48	77.44	-10.57	-3.15	65.30	60.80	29.75	4.06	5.74	1
13	Uniform	v	0.48	0.55	3.29	20.09	23.39	-82.08	-14.69	363.65	-250.75	-98.53	77.43	73.39	39.19	27.10	24.47	0.69
14				0.74	2.69	4.28	9.19	-19.32	-3.31	77.43	-31.24	-13.29	75.05	70.77	42.77	17.17	15.10	1
15				0.90	2.56	2.98	9.02	-13.69	-2.32	53.95	-12.38	-4.85	74.63	70.33	39.18	8.99	11.10	1
16				1.10	2.42	2.63	9.66	-12.35	-2.06	47.70	-5.97	-1.69	74.11	69.77	28.24	3.53	7.60	1
17	Non-Uniform	x, v	0.72	0.74	1.69	4.80	9.24	0.00	-4.15	87.67	-43.22	-18.84	100	95.61	44.43	21.49	23.12	1
18				0.90	1.66	4.40	9.01	0.00	0.00	80.36	-39.93	-17.14	100	100	43.57	21.33	24.44	1
19	Uniform	x, v	0.72	0.74	2.49	2.76	8.53	0.00	-2.25	50.43	-22.03	-9.46	100	96.24	42.96	18.77	21.52	1
20				0.90	2.44	2.58	8.44	0.00	0.00	47.06	-20.66	-8.88	100	100	42.98	19.00	23.14	1
21	Non-Uniform	v	0.72	0.55	4.72	5.92	10.64	-25.89	-3.61	107.10	-73.49	-27.94	75.83	72.46	38.02	26.09	18.30	0.03
22				0.74	3.69	20.04	23.73	-111.85	-15.49	362.23	-206.03	-86.74	69.12	64.85	42.10	23.95	20.61	0.52
23				0.90	3.52	10.44	17.03	-62.50	-8.46	188.72	-68.55	-27.11	66.88	62.40	39.55	14.37	12.96	1
24				1.10	3.16	6.78	15.20	-41.06	-5.48	122.56	-23.79	-6.79	66.49	62.02	28.52	5.54	7.54	1
25				0.55	0	0	7.39	-15.01	-3.06	133.67	-58.91	-22.06	88.77	86.48	37.44	16.50	16.50	0
26	Uniform	v	0.72	0.74	4.47	9.1	12.55	-37.80	-6.73	164.87	-92.01	-38.62	77.07	72.99	41.98	23.43	17.46	0.82
27				0.90	4.06	5.26	13.50	-22.90	-3.99	95.22	-31.51	-12.14	75.95	71.77	38.63	12.75	12.65	1
28				1.10	3.74	4.02	13.58	-17.94	-3.09	72.84	-13.26	-3.63	75.37	71.13	27.40	4.99	8.23	1

Mode C: A summary of the results for the studied system, such as preheating/charging time and solar/charging efficiencies is presented in Table 16.

Table 15. Summary of results for the envisaged system (Mode C).

Case	Heat flux profile	Losses abs	Sidewalls losses	Crucible H (m)	t_{pr} (h)	t_c (h)	η_{abs} (%)	η_c (%)	dev1 ¹ (%)	dev2 ² (%)	Q_{stored}/m_{PCM} (MJ/kg)	$T_{ave, PCM, LFR0}$ (K) ³	$T_{ave, PCM, LFR1}$ (K) ³	DT (K)
1	Uniform	x	0.24	0.24	1.07	0.84	100	-	-	-	1.30	1342.47	1607.88	~265
2				0.48	2.21	1.66	-	-	1.17	1375.11	1592.90	~218		
3				0.72	3.36	2.41	-	-	1.10	1390.38	1571.43	~181		
4	Non-Uniform	x	0.24	0.24	0.94	1.05	100	25.53	-	-	1.63	1240.51	1664.89	~424
5				0.48	1.54	2.64	58.88	-	1.96	1094.36	1695.98	~602		
6				0.72	2.31	3.79	56.85	-	1.72	1095.42	1642.61	~547		
7	Uniform	v	0.24	0.24	1.09	0.87	100	93.75	-	3.64	1.27	1348.38	1598.46	~250
8				0.48	2.26	1.75	93.18	-	5.24	1380.70	1585.78	~205		
9				0.72	3.44	2.56	93.19	-	5.85	1392.90	1608.94	~216		
10	Non-Uniform	v	0.24	0.24	0.96	1.09	93.51	25.74	3.82	1.80	1249.04	1654.34	~405	
11				0.48	1.58	2.78	92.86	58.94	5.28	1104.47	1685.98	~582		
12				0.72	2.38	3.99	93.04	55.96	5.25	1108.31	1635.70	~527		
13	Uniform	v	0.24	0.24	1.17	1.15	70.78	64.90	-	37.70	1.15	1343.45	1539.40	~196
14				0.48	2.44	2.22	73.60	67.14	-	33.65	1.04	1368.63	1525.49	~157
15				0.72	3.66	3.26	74.79	68.30	-	35.04	1.01	1385.16	1514.66	~129
16	Non-Uniform	v	0.24	0.24	1.13	1.38	66.96	60.90	19.81	31.43	1.29	1307.34	1574.89	~268
17				0.48	2.01	3.62	64.89	58.10	62.78	36.93	1.46	1203.86	1593.31	~389
18				0.72	3.16	5.13	66.07	59.25	57.47	35.58	1.37	1223.47	1569.56	~346

¹Deviation of charging time t_c of the non-uniform profile from the uniform profile.

²Deviation for each height from cases 1-6 (uniform with uniform, and, non-uniform with non-uniform profiles are being compared).

³ $T_{ave, PCM, LFR0}$ and $T_{ave, PCM, LFR1}$ average PCM temperature right before the start and right after the PCM melting

Mode D: A summary of the results for the envisaged system, such as discharging time and conversion efficiency is presented in Table 17.

Table 16. Summary of results for the envisaged system (Mode D).

Case	Lateral losses	Crucible H_c (m)	TPV E_g (eV)	t_d^1 (h)	t_d^2 (h)	$\bar{\eta}_d(\%)$	$\bar{\eta}_{TPV}(\%)$	$\bar{\eta}_{d,el}(\%)$
47	v	0.24	0.55	2.43	2.57	86.31	39.42	34.02
48			0.74	3.60	3.98	76.56	41.35	31.65
49			0.90	5.01	5.65	64.77	37.33	24.18
50			1.10	6.75	7.73	50.58	25.33	12.81
51			0.55	2.68	2.84	100	39.45	39.45
52	x	0.24	0.74	4.43	4.87	100	41.50	41.50
53			0.90	7.18	8.09	100	37.64	37.64
54			1.10	12.50	14.02	100	25.63	25.63
55	v	0.48	0.55	2.64	2.75	93.19	39.37	36.69
56			0.74	4.20	4.51	87.70	41.18	36.12
56			0.90	6.34	6.90	80.13	37.08	29.71
58			1.10	9.50	10.43	68.78	24.44	16.81
59			0.55	2.71	2.92	100	39.40	39.40
60	x	0.48	0.74	4.51	4.93	100	41.31	41.31
61			0.90	7.31	8.12	100	37.36	37.36
62			1.10	12.62	14.09	100	24.88	24.88
63	v	0.72	0.55	2.70	2.90	95.53	39.41	37.65
64			0.74	4.39	4.89	91.83	41.35	37.97
65			0.90	6.93	7.79	86.47	37.37	32.31
66			1.10	10.99	12.46	77.75	24.90	19.36
67			0.55	2.75	2.85	100	39.45	39.45
68	x	0.72	0.74	4.55	4.86	100	41.50	41.50
69			0.90	7.51	8.22	100	37.62	37.62
70			1.10	12.82	14.29	100	25.10	25.10

¹ The time needed for the PCM to solidify 2 Monitored in the main text as t_d . Contains as well the time needed for the emitter to reach the PCM solidification point

Supplementary parameters

A. Temperature uniformity index

In this sub-section the temperature uniformity is assessed along all three main modes of operation (Modes C/D, C and D) at two key surfaces, i.e. the absorber sidewalls and the TPV emitter surface. For the purpose of this analysis, the area-weighted average of the temperature uniformity index (UI) is plotted with time.

The UI represents how a specific scalar variable varies over a surface with 1 signifying perfect uniformity. The area-weighted average UI of temperature is defined as:

$$UI = 1 - \frac{\sum_i^n [(T_i - \bar{T}_a) A_i]}{2|\bar{T}_a| \sum_i^n A_i} \quad \text{Equation 19}$$

, where i is a cell facet of a surface with n facets and \bar{T}_a is the average value of T over the surface.

Mode C/D:

Figure 30. Temperature uniformity index with time for A) $H_c = 0.24$ m, B) $H_c = 0.48$ m, and C) $H_c = 0.72$ m. (Solid line: Absorber sidewalls, Dotted line: TPV surface). **Mode C/D – Non-Uniform heat flux profile**

Mode C: For the absorber sidewalls in Mode C, results show that at greater heights ($H_c > 0.48$ m), temperature uniformity decreases under a non-uniform heat flux profile ($UI < 0.9$), while it

remains nearly uniform for the uniform case throughout PCM melting. The strongest non-uniformity occurs during the PCM pre-heating phase, before melting begins. Once a liquid film forms, the buoyancy-driven natural convection within the liquid phase helps homogenize the temperature. This underscores the importance of utilizing solid-liquid phase change materials in ultra-high temperature solar-driven applications. Additionally, due to the TPV emitter's proximity to the solar absorber, some temperature non-uniformity appears at this surface. However, in this mode, the TPV converter is detached, leaving the TPV cell unaffected.

Figure 31. Temperature uniformity index with time for A) $H_c = 0.24$ m, B) $H_c = 0.48$ m, and C) $H_c = 0.72$ m. (Solid line: Absorber sidewalls, Dotted line: TPV surface). **Mode C**

Mode D: Throughout the PCM discharging phase, the temperature profile at the TPV emitter surface remains nearly uniform. Notably, the TPV cells—positioned in close proximity to the emitter, within a micrometer-scale range—will receive an almost uniform heat flux (W/m^2).

Figure 32. Temperature uniformity index with time for A) $H_c = 0.24$ m, B) $H_c = 0.48$ m, and C) $H_c = 0.72$ m. (Solid line: TPV surface). **Mode D**

Mode S: This mode primarily serves as a storage phase but remains in a slow self-discharging state due to unavoidable lateral thermal losses. Heat is extracted gradually, and thermal insulation is applied to minimize further dissipation. As a result, the operating conditions are not analyzed in terms of temperature uniformity at the TPV emitter or absorber sidewalls, making the uniformity index irrelevant to this study.

Acknowledgments

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie SHINE (GA:101145914) and SUNSON (GA:101083827). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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A.G.: Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Formal Analysis, **T.D.:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization, Investigation, **A.D.:** Writing-original draft, Conceptualization, Investigation, Supervising

Declaration of interests

The current work is related to a patent application ES2991113 entitled as "Acumulador y convertidor de energía solar térmica" with Alejandro Datas Medina being the principal investigator and Thorsten Denk related investigator.

Declaration of generative ai and ai-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the author(s) used chatGPT in order to edit the produced text. After using this tool/service, the author(s) reviewed and edited the content as needed and take(s) full responsibility for the content of the publication.

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